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Layers of Lexical Borrowing in Long-Term Contact Rooted among Ancient Crops from Mali's Bandiagara Region

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Abstract

In this research, the People and Plants method illuminates language interactions in Eastern Mali's Bandiagara Region. Home to six linguistic groups, the Bandiagara Escarpment has sheltered two populations for at least 800 years, though their pre-cliff origins are unclear. Historical empires might have driven them to this defensible terrain, with fertile lands anchoring them. Notably, evidence points to early pearl millet domestication not far from here, a Sahelian staple, around 5,000 years ago. Examining current plant-related lexemes across local languages and contrasting with distant, unrelated languages offers insights into older forms. Merging these findings with external data depicts language contact layers. Modern Bandiagara residents, likely with pre-existing botanical knowledge, may have been influenced by the 'Mande Expansion' and its vast West African trade routes.

Keywords

loan words – pre-colonial West Africa – migration – agriculture – language isolates

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1 Introduction

The Bandiagara Region where this study takes place is located in the West African Sahel. The Bandiagara Region is defined here as encompassing the Bandiagara Escarpment, including its Plateau, as well as the valleys formed from tributaries of the Niger River that traverse the cliffs, and the sandy plains surrounding the mountain range. The area is home to a diverse mix of ethnic groups speaking various languages with uncertain or debated genealogical classifications, who have been in contact for a prolonged duration. These languages include Bangime, an isolate, the Dogon languages, and several important Mande varieties – both of these groups currently occupy their own branches of the Niger-Congo phylum that dominates Africa, as well as the Atlantic language Fulfulde – and two Songhay languages tentatively included in the Nilo-Saharan phylum. A map illustrating villages of the Bandiagara Region and its respective spoken languages is provided in Map 1.

The Bandiagara Region is a locus of early human development in West Africa. Notably, the name of the city which lies at the heart of the Escarpment, ‘Bandiagara’ [bàndzà-gàrá] can be translated as an archaic Dogon form for, ‘a large wooden eating bowl made by the blacksmith caste for offering food in ceremonies.’¹ The inception of agriculture is estimated to have taken place just to the north of this region where several modern widely cultivated plant species were first domesticated, and the oldest pottery dated in sub-Saharan Africa was found in an archeological site at the Bandiagara Escarpment.

Furthermore, by force of proximity, as well as the adjacent Niger River as a source of trade and therefore, communication (McIntosh and McIntosh, 1988), all of these ethno-linguistic groups have been in close contact over an extended period of time, thus shared vocabulary abound throughout their unrelated languages.

An examination and comparison of the Bandiagara Region (hereafter simply BR)’s lexica for its peoples’ most commonly cultivated crops offers a window to the linguistic and cultural diversity which once was found across West Africa. Because the settlement patterns of BR are also not fully understood, evidence from *Wanderworts* exchanged through language contact can direct us to past pathways and ancient trade routes.

1 Dogon lexical data and village coordinates are drawn from the author’s database and <https://dogonlanguages.info/>. Each map is also available in an interactive version in the Supplemental Materials (<https://osf.io/8jkgx/>).

MAP 1 Bandiagara linguistic diversity (Mali)

2 Background

Before delving into comparative crop terms, an awareness of the importance of BR to West Africa as a whole is crucial. In order to obtain a better picture of the factors that have potentially affected and shaped the past of the peoples that live here today and their languages, a timeline is henceforth depicted that captures our current understanding of the area in its archeological agricultural context as well as the historical development of the major West African empires.

2.1 *Early Human Development in BR*

The earliest pottery in sub-Saharan Africa was found at a network of sites known as Ounjougou, located on the Bandiagara Plateau and adjacent plains dated to 9400 cal BC (Huyscom et al., 2009).² The first uses of pottery generally correspond with pre-agriculture practices. That is, the ceramics found at Ounjougou were used to boil gathered edible wild *Panicoid* grasses during the humid phases of the Holocene era. The domestication of wild plants was actually a secondary subsistence method to hunting and gathering (Kahlheber and Neumann, 2007).

Using native grains in cooking, and later planting, represented the beginnings of a transition from the gathering of wild millet species to the farming of domesticated millet. Domesticated pearl millet (formerly *Pennisetum glaucum*

² The Ounjougou archaeological site is located next to the contemporary, Mombo Dogon-speaking village, Ondougou. Note that many Dogon-inhabited villages' names are composed compounds with the word *-dougou* [dugu] which corresponds to the word for 'village' in the Mande language Bambara.

Phase	Pottery	Domesticated pearl millet		Domesticated African rice	Complex societies
Site(s)	Ounjougou	Er Negf	Ounjougou	Dia Shoma	Jenne-Jenno
Timeline	pre-9000	2010-1670	1800-800	800-200	350-250
	BC				AD
Source	(Soriano and Huysecom, 2011; Huysecom et al., 2009)		(Fuller et al., 2021)	(McIntosh and McIntosh, 1981)	

FIGURE 1 Earliest human development in West Africa featured in BR

now *Cenchrus americanus*) dated to 2579-2409BC, has been found approximately 200 kilometers to the northeast of BR at the archeological site Er Negf in the Lower Tilemsi Valley (Manning et al., 2011). Ozainne et al. (2014: 359) associate the domestication of pearl millet with the dawn of agriculture in West Africa; a process that would take thousands of years and eventually cause populations to migrate and separate into distinctive groups speaking diverging languages throughout West Africa.

Consequently, for emerging farming communities, sedentary lifestyles replaced pastoral practices, which in turn gave rise to growing settlements and expansive trade networks. BR became a junction for intricate webs of exchange between groups living in the arid areas of the Sahara to those further south. The sites of Dia-Shoma and Djenné-Djenno, both located adjacent to the modern-day city of Djenné, about 200 kilometers southwest of BR, are considered the most ancient urban centers in West Africa (Haskell, McIntosh, and McIntosh, 1988). In addition to being hubs where people could exchange, for example salt from the north with fish from the south, Africa’s first rice farmers probably inhabited the Inner Niger Delta (McIntosh and McIntosh, 1981) of this region. It has even been suggested that the origin of ethnicities in today’s Sahel region of West Africa came about at these ancient cities in response to agricultural expansion and societal occupational roles (Gallais, 1984).

A summary of these archeological sites is provided in Figure 1 and Map 2 shows the locations of the archeological sites listed in Figure 1.

Naturally, this list of four sites is not exhaustive, but it was at these specific locations that major events as pertains to this study occurred. Many more Sahelian West Africa sites have been studied from an archeological and historical points of view than can be dealt with in this paper. Some of them are discussed in further detail in the comparative portion of this paper. Those that are, are included in the full version of the map included with the supplemental

MAP 2 West African early human development sites in and near BR

materials (<https://osf.io/8jkgx/>). The following subsection presents the historical context that has most impacted the populations living in BR today.

2.2 *West African Empires and Dominant lingua francae*

Three major West African imperial reigns are discussed in this study. The first of which, the Ghana Empire, covered modern-day western Mali and eastern Mauritania from 300 or 400 to 1100AD (Brooks, 1993; Kea, 2004). Fage (1957) reports that ‘Ghana’ as the ‘Land of Gold’ was first written about by the Persian astronomer Ibrahim al-Fazari in 788–793AD. The Ghana Empire was clearly prosperous.

According to historians, the Ghana Empire was known by its autochthones as Wagadou, and was founded by the Soninke ethno-linguistic group (Kone, 2018). Soninke is one of the Mande languages mentioned above that is still spoken in BR today. In the year 1240AD, the Ghana Empire was destroyed, either by Almoravids (Moroccan Berbers) or by the forthcoming Mali Empire founder Soundiata Keita (Mauny 1961, citing historian Abū Ubayd al-Bakri). In an eminent article discussed in detail below by the Ounjougou archeological team, Mayor et al. (2005: 30) note, “The collapse of this Empire generated a large diaspora towards the River Niger”, citing that which anthropologists Dieterlen, Diarra and Soumare (1992: 188) refer to as the “Soninke Diaspora”. The collapse of the Ghana Empire precipitated a population dispersal and integration into Dia (the ancient city whose archeological site is mentioned as Dia-Shoma above). The very definition of the ethnic groups today known as the Bozo, (a Mande ethnolinguistic group who fish along the Niger River and are closely related to the Soninke) and Dogon were thought to have been first delineated from this diaspora (Fay, 1997).

As noted, the Soninke language forms part of the Mande family which either stands on its own or constitutes a separate branch within the broadly reach-

FIGURE 2 Mande classification

P.C. VALENTIN VYDRIN 2023, BASED ON VYDRIN, 2009

ing Niger-Congo language phylum (Eberhard, Simons and Fennig, 2021). The Bozo people speak numerous Bozo languages; their speakers are the inferred earliest rice cultivators of the Inner Niger Delta mentioned above, who also practice fishing today. Bozo fishing people currently live along the Niger River. Those who occupy the valley leading into the Bandiagara Escarpment are the only known Bozo who practice millet farming. Their Bozo language, *Jenaama*, translates to ‘the people of Djenné’, which refers to one of the first cities established in West Africa as noted above.

The second empire that impacted groups living in BR today is that of the Songhay. Although the Songhay Empire only lasted from between the mid-15th to late 16th centuries AD, its capital city, Gao, has had significant pre-imperial political organization going back to the 7th century (Cissé et al., 2013). Linguistically, Songhay consists of a group of languages which hold a disputed position within the Nilo-Saharan phylum (Souag, 2012; Dimmendaal, 2014; Bendor-Samuel, 2000; Nicolai, 2003), different to that of the Dogon and Mande language groups. Note that nomadic “Sorko” (a caste of Bozo fishermen) who currently live along the Niger River from Djenné to Dendi (located in present-day Benin) co-inhabited and eventually assimilated with Songhay agriculturalists in the 5th and 6th centuries AD (Simonis, 2010: 55).

The third major empire to be discussed here, Mali, with its heart at “Mande” – a quasi-mythical homeland from which the majority of BR ethno-linguistic groups claim to have come – lasted from the 13th to 15th century AD (Roberts, 1987). Although the Mali Empire did not last as long as that of Ghana, its effects were far-reaching. The term “Mande Expansion” was first used by historian George Brooks (1993) in reference to the progressively southward movement of Mande-speaking warriors from the increasingly aridifying Sahara from 1100–1500AD. Yet, the author states that the raiders were but the second of two

FIGURE 3 Timeline of major West African empires

Mande Expansions in which the former constituted trading peoples along the trans-Saharan routes from the far north to the central West African coast.³ The Mande Expansion can be credited with the fact that today, the Mande ethnolinguistic group to which Soninke, Bozo, and today's lingua franca of Mali, Bambara, belong, consists of 75 languages and 172 dialects (Hammarström et al., 2022) spoken by upwards of 30 to 40 million people (Vydrin, 2009).

The last empire to be discussed whose people have affected today's BR ethnolinguistic groups is the Macina Empire. Fula were the rulers of a brief pre-colonial Muslim state based on strict Sharia rule (Bâ and Daget, 1962). However, this short reign is not the only impact of the people nor their language on BR. The Fula language of the region, Macina Fulfulde, is spoken across Mali and Niger and thus serves as a *lingua franca* for many non-related ethnolinguistic groups, including those of BR. Fula herders roam with their livestock across all of Sahelian Africa and thus speakers of their languages number in the millions today.

Figure 3 illustrates a timeline of the four major West African empires whose inhabitants' spoken languages have impacted BR. Dates are given in AD format. Locations of the presumed capitals of each empire are given on Map 3.

As shown on Map 3, BR is located at the heart of the three largest West African Empires and is immediately adjacent to Macina. As presented in the following subsection, the Bandiagara Escarpment itself served as a refuge zone for populations who fled the consequences of these imposing and expanding empires.

2.3 *The Bandiagara Escarpment*

The Bandiagara Escarpment forms the basis for BR and is home to the celebrated Dogon peoples as well as the Bangande, speakers of the language isolate Bangime. Following the ethnographic research of Marcel Griaule (1938),

3 A major Mande group, the Jula, derive their name from the Soninke term *jùlâ* meaning 'merchant' or 'trader'. Their language serves as a language of trade as well as the *lingua franca* of several countries in West Africa today.

MAP 3 Locations of major West African empire capital cities

the cliff range drew the attention of outsiders by a Dutch team of archaeologists whose research took place in the 1960's. Quite remarkable in their construction, shelters built into the face of the Escarpment were first documented by Bedaux (1972). His team and subsequent authors have adopted the word "*Tellem*" [*télém*] a term used by Dogon speakers primarily found in the northeastern parts of the Bandiagara Escarpment, to describe the people who purportedly built these structures.⁴

More recently, a major outcome of the Ounjougou archeological research group highlighted above was the establishment of a continuous timeline of human inhabitation of the Bandiagara Escarpment for the past 3,000 years (Mayor and Huysecom, 2016; Mayor et al., 2005). Mayor et al. (2005) provide a complete overview from the perspectives of previous ethnographers and historians, as well as revisiting prior archeological evidence, to argue, through their own archaeological and paleo-climatological research, that the Dogon came to settle the Bandiagara Escarpment sometime around 500–800 years ago. Specifically, Mayor et al. (2014) demonstrate that prior to the Dogon, different groups – a cultural “mosaic” – lived along the cliff range as an area not only suitable to farming, but also, in more recent times, as a sanctuary from the threat of the imposing empires described above.

The diagram in Figure 4 illustrates a timeline of the first settlers of the Bandiagara Escarpment up to the present day. According to the proposed timeline, Dogon populations began settling the Bandiagara Escarpment between 1230 and 1430AD (Mayor et al., 2005).

4 Although Mayor et al. (2014) suggest that *Tellem* means ‘those before’ and Blom (2011) translates it as ‘we have found them’, neither of these glosses were found in the current lexical database; the actual meaning remains unknown.

Bedaux (1972)

Mayor et al. (2005)

FIGURE 4 Bandiagara Escarpment population settlement timeline

Note: The once proposed hiatus was replaced by Mayor et al (2016) with a conclusion of continuous inhabitation.

It has been proposed that Fula (speakers of the Atlantic language Fulfulde) slave raiders (van Beek, 1992) pushed the Dogon to seek refuge in the Bandiagara Escarpment. Although Fula have been frequently found throughout West Africa at least since the 13th century (Fay, 1997), contact between Dogon and Fula populations is thought to have not occurred until the 17th century onwards (Mayor et al., 2005: 30). Therefore, if their estimations are correct, Dogon settlement would pre-date contact with Fula peoples. And yet, the benefits of the Bandiagara Escarpment as a protection zone are clear (Nunn and Puga, 2012; Mayor et al., 2005). According to the proposed timeline, Dogon peoples more likely sought refuge from the disintegrating Ghana Empire than Fula kidnapers.

Mayor et al. (2005) additionally state that in the 16th century, Songhay peoples tried to conquer the Dogon. Many North Plateau Dogon-speaking villages are still known to outsiders by Songhay names.⁵ Some Songhay, speakers of the Songhay language Tondi Kiini, still occupy isolated hills to the northeast of the Escarpment where Nangan Dogon languages are spoken today. Otherwise, save for market interactions and travel, most Dogon and Songhay populations do not interact on a daily basis and do not speak each other's languages.

Although the Dogon are labeled as one cohesive group, they speak at least 20 disparate languages and number a little over 600,000 (Eberhard, Simons, and Fennig, 2021). In terms of time depth based on lexicostatistics methods

⁵ Some examples are *Koira Beiri* 'big town', *Ibissa* 'I have passed', *Borko* [*bòrkin*] 'noble', and *Tondifere* [*tóndi*] 'stone'.

FIGURE 5 Dogon classification
 Note: Preliminary Dogon neighbor-joining phylogenetic tree created with Ape package (Paradis and Schliep, 2019) for R using methods and data employed in Hantgan et al. (2022)

(Prokhorov et al., 2012; Moran and Prokić, 2013), as well as preliminary Bayesian statistics (Hantgan, 2021), the most recent Dogon splits happened around 500–700 years ago. While these divisions would neatly fall in line with the trajectory for Dogon settlement of the Bandiagara Escarpment, the Dogon language group as a whole may go back at least 2,000 years. The timespan mismatch can be attributed to the presence of Dogon peoples and languages existing somewhere prior to their occupation of the cliffs.

In current times, Dogon communities are mostly small and agronomic, but they also practice horticulture; they inhabit the plateau, stone promontories on the slopes, and, increasingly, many villages in the sandy plains from the eastern Escarpment to the border with Burkina Faso. Members of Dogon villages communicate with each other through more widely spoken Dogon languages such as Tommo So and Jamsay, or via Macina Fulfulde. Through travel and schooling, some Dogon people learn to speak other languages, but a knowledge of Fulfulde is sufficient for even market commerce and local purposes.

The only other ethnicity who live on or along the Bandiagara Escarpment is the Bangande, speakers of Bangime, who claim a common ancestry with Dogon peoples. As all archaeological and most ethnographic research with Dogon peoples has been focused on the southeastern portions of the Bandiagara Escarpment located a relatively long distance from the area where Bangime is spoken today, their provenance remains unknown.

Today, the Bangande are patrilineal and are a mixed group ethnographically: the majority are exogamous while some are strictly endogamous. Women who marry into the Bangande group are often from surrounding Dogon villages. Eventually, they acquire Bangime as do their children. Otherwise, indigenous

Bangande do not speak any Dogon language. They speak Fulfulde with Dogon-speaking neighbors. Some Bangande who travel to the cities learn Bambara. Due to an inherited taboo relationship between Dogon and Bozo ancestors, there is little (if any) bilingualism between Dogon (and Bangande as they claim a common lineage) and Bozo (Mande) peoples even though the Jenaama Bozo are the closest neighbors of the Bangande.

As noted in the previous section, the plethora of Mande languages spoken across West Africa can be attributed to the Mande Expansion. The consequence of this Expansion is the complex long-term contact scenario that incorporates internal convergence and borrowing from *lingua francae* that are blurred by migrations and language shifts. Yet, the only Mande languages that are currently spoken in BR are Bambara, Bozo, and Soninke, and none of these is spoken on or along the Escarpment itself. No Mande populations speak any Dogon varieties or Bangime and their current contact with Songhay speakers is also limited to markets and cities such as Djenne.

With materials and methods presented in the following section, the current study integrates evidence of this long-term language contact scenario with genetic, historic, and archeological findings in the domain of domesticated plants and animals among these groups living on and along the Escarpment and in BR to trace a time map of its settlement patterns. In the interest of conserving length, only seven domesticated plant species are treated in this article. Domestication is defined in this study as the deliberate selection and subsequent cultivation of a plant which was previously gathered in the wild. As noted above and treated in detail in the sections to follow, three crops which are essential to the lives of BR farmers today were domesticated in the contiguous area. Although the names for these species are intrinsically ancient, it will be shown that phonetic patterns remain recognizable in the vocabularies of the languages treated in this study using the methods described in the following section.

3 Materials and Methods

This study builds on on-going work (Hantgan and List, 2022; Hantgan et al., 2022). The database used for those studies is currently being expanded for the purposes of this, as well as additional computationally-supported research; it is available with the materials accompanying Hantgan and List (2022). For the present purposes, in order to supplement linguistic, as well as cultural and botanical data gathered from the Bandiagara Escarpment (<https://dogonlanguages.info/>), the Pan-African database, RefLex (Segerer and Flavier, 2022), housed

at the CNRS unit LLACAN, was actively consulted. With over one and a half million entries and counting, this is the perfect resource to search for evidence of language contact between speakers of the languages of BR and those of unrelated, non-neighboring languages and peoples.⁶

3.1 *Materials*

Data are drawn from two primary sources: the Dogon and Bangime Linguistics project materials (<https://dogonlanguages.info/>) and Reflex (<http://reflex.cnrs.fr/>). The entire dataset is included in the supplemental materials (<https://osf.io/8jkgx/>) with citations to all the sources consulted, as well as each language's family, glottocode, and the GPS coordinates from where the data were collected.

Table 1 lists the BR languages used in this study, classified according to the Glottolog 4.7 (<https://glottolog.org/>, Hammarström et al., 2022), with the exception that both Mande and Dogon are listed therein as constituting their own independent families. Here, disputed phyla are given in parentheses.

All languages included in this study are spoken in BR and were either associated with major West African empires (Mande, Songhay, Macina), or are spoken by populations who were directly affected by those empires (Bangime, Dogon). These languages were also selected because of the availability of a wide range of data including geographic locations, comprehensive lexicons, and descriptions of nominal phonology and morphology.⁷ As illustrated in Map 1, the language sample is relatively representative of BR. For the majority of lexica, names of plant species were confirmed with multiple speakers and identified both by fieldworkers and two independent biologists, however, a more comprehensive survey including languages from areas not shown on the map is planned for the near future.⁸

The entire database from which data from these languages are drawn contains 38 languages and words associated with 348 concepts for both borrowing-resistant words and those which are susceptible to being borrowed.⁹ A previous

6 Unfortunately, Mali, in particular BR, has been inaccessible to any external researchers for around 10 years due to political unrest. On the other hand, language data are abundant for the entire area thanks to the thorough documentation of the Dogon and Bangime Linguistics Project that took place from 2005–2010 (<https://dogonlanguages.info/>, managed by Moran et al., 2016).

7 For the present purposes, only nouns were analyzed. Future studies will include verbs in the agricultural domain as well.

8 Especially Gur languages are the next group of languages to be included in the comparative database.

9 A concept is defined here as being associated with the universal set contained in the Concepticon (List et al., 2022).

TABLE 1 List of BR languages classified according to Hammarström et al. (2022)

Language family	Subgroup	Varieties
Isolate	–	Bangime
(Niger-Congo) Dogon	Escarpment Nangan North Plateau Plains West	Donno So, Tommo So, Toro So (Ibi So), Toro So, Yorno So Bankan Tey, Ben Tey, Nanga Dogul Dom, Yanda Dom, Bondu So (Najamba-Kindige), Tebul Ure Gourou, Jamsay, Perge Tegu, Togo Kan, Tomo Kan, Toro Tegu Ampari, Bunoge, Mombo, Penange, Tiranige Diga
(Niger-Congo) Mande North Western Mande	East-Manding Soninke-Bozo	Bambara Jenaama, Soninke
Niger-Congo Atlantic-Congo North-Central Atlantic	North Atlantic Fula	Macina Fulfulde
(Nilo-Saharan) Songhay	Eastern	Tondi Kiini, Humburi Senni, Djenné Chiini

study using the larger dataset found that an area of the languages' lexica which was highlighted as comprising probable loans (Hantgan and List, 2022) was that of agriculture. Agricultural terms (domesticated plants and animals) were thus selected to be compared with an even wider range of languages than thus far considered.

The taxa chosen for this study include pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*),¹⁰ sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*), fonio (*Digitaria exilis*), rice (*Oryza glaberrima*),

¹⁰ Here, the species name *Pennisetum glaucum* will be retained to refer to the cultivated variety of pearl millet rather than the new denomination *Cenchrus americanus* in order to remain consistent with the literature.

maize (*Zea mays*), okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*), manioc/cassava/sweet potato (*Dioscorea rotundata*, *Manihot esculenta*, and *Ipomoea batatas*), and peanut ('Bambara groundnut' *Vigna subterranea*). Each of these plants are cultivated crops in BR and remain indispensable to the agriculture practices of groups living in BR. These specific species were selected for two reasons: a) they are believed to have been first domesticated in or near BR (pearl millet, rice, and possibly fonio) and thus likely attest indigenous names or b) were imported to the area and thus probably consist of loan words (maize, manioc/cassava, and peanut).

For the current study, the selection of BR languages and concepts was complemented by pan-African data gathered from RefLex (Segeer and Flavier, 2022) as well as individual dictionaries of targeted languages where relevant, using the methods as described in the following subsection. In total, 583 lexical items were implicated in the study across 161 separately named languages.

3.2 *Methods*

As noted in the previous subsection, the current comparison of words for cultivated plant species in BR builds on prior, as well as on-going, research on the lexica of the languages spoken in the area. The process of raw data conversion to Cross-Linguistic Data Formats (Forkel et al., 2018) is presented in the afore mentioned study, (Hantgan and List, 2022). Table 2 provides an excerpt of words for the concept MILLET (Concepticon concepts are represented in capital letters) in several BR languages in order to illustrate how the data appear in the original comparative database.

First, each entry is assigned a unique ID which also contains the source gloss. From there, original values are manually transformed into consistently parsed morphological forms with compounds divided into two words with a space in between and roots separated from suffixes by hyphens. Then, each grapheme is prepared for segmentation and eventual alignment. As some of the sources do not mark tones or vowel length, each segment is given an alternative transcription without diacritics. The concepts chosen for the current study are those which we found in our previous study to be likely loan words with the methods to do so also described therein (Hantgan and List, 2022). The processed data are analyzed and visualized using the web-based tool Edictor (List, 2021).

The data excerpt of words for the concept MILLET drawn from the larger comparative dataset illustrates the ease of visualization by colors differentiating sound patterns. Furthermore, each noun stem is assigned a cognate number (COGID), each individual root and affix are given separate cognate identifiers (COGIDS), and applicable stems are also assigned to a borrowing set (BORID). These assignments can each be adjusted by hand within the Edictor tool itself.

TABLE 2 Excerpt from raw data after being processed with CLDF workflow

Language ID and source	Value	Form	Graphemes	Segments	Concepticon ID	Concepticon Concept
Bangime-855_millet-1 (hantbang)	démè	dé-mè	^ d é + m è \$	d é + m è	931	MILLET
BozoDebo-162_mil-1 (smeltzerbozo)	jɛŋ	dʒɛŋ	^ j ɛ ŋ \$	dʒ ɛ ŋ	931	MILLET
BozoPondorisud-162_mil-1 (smeltzerbozo)	jɛpɪ	dʒɛ pɪ	^ j ɛ + p ɪ \$	dʒ ɛ + p ɪ	931	MILLET
BozoTieyaxo-162_mil-1 (smeltzerbozo)	jʏɛ	dʒʏɛ	^ jʏ ɛ \$	dʒʏ ɛ	931	MILLET
Jamsay Douentza-6046_millet-1	ɲú:	ɲúú	^ ɲ ú: \$	ɲ/ɲ ú:/u:	931	MILLET
Bozo Korondougou nord-162_mil-1 (smeltzerbozo)	pɪi	pɪi	^ p ɪ i \$	p ɪ:	931	MILLET
Bunoge-6046_millet-1 (heathdogon)	sé:ŋgè	sée-ŋgè	^ s é:- ŋ g è \$	s é:/e: + ʔ g è/e	931	MILLET
DogulDom-6046_millet-1 (heathdogon)	siyé	sijé	^ s i y é \$	s i/i j é/ɛ	931	MILLET

I incorporated lexical additions from RefLex (Segerer and Flavier, 2022) using the tool's built-in 'search for borrowing' feature. In order to use this device, I selected words which we had analyzed as being potentially shared but not cognate with related languages in the sample. Then I searched in the RefLex database within a group of languages with which BR speakers were likely to have been in contact. That is, in terms of examples treated in Table 2 and Figure 6 above, Bangime, Dogon, and Bozo speakers are known to have been in contact with speakers of additional Mande languages. Thus, I further explored these languages for common lexemes. However, because loan words with a deep time depth are likely to have changed from the source language to adapt to the target language's phonotactics, another level of searching was required in RefLex using a simplified phonetic code. Therefore, I followed a subsequent step by looking for lexemes with codes which are the same and, optionally, glossed as associated, with a particular concept. The optionality of selecting a given concept is helpful as words inevitably shift meaning over time. These two processes are shown in the excerpt from the RefLex interface in Figure 7.

Because RefLex data comes from African languages across the continent, it is not necessary to limit the search to the study's target area. In fact, long distance loans are of particular interest because these may indicate avenues of

FIGURE 6 Excerpt of processed data as visualized and editable in Edictor

FIGURE 7 Results from ‘search for borrowing’ in RefLex within and across language families for the concept MILLET

trade or previous contact with speakers who do not currently neighbor any BR speakers. Consequently, I expanded the search beyond the study area.

The phonetic codes shown in Figure 7 are already integrated into the RefLex database which makes searching for distant contact convenient and relatively simple. The codes are essentially simplified versions of a lexeme where each individual phoneme is converted into a broader sound within its manner and/or place of articulation. The example shown in Figure 7 of reflexes for the

concept MILLET combines the sounds *ɲ, *y, and *j as J and *o and *ɔ as O. These changes are typologically regular and expected, and thus these patterns can be considered to be reliable.

I then grouped each lexeme according to these phonetic codes and plotted the codes on interactive maps for each concept (hyperlinks are provided in the supplemental materials <https://osf.io/8jkgx/> to each plot). I created all the maps used in this paper using LingTypology (Moroz, 2017), a package for R (R Core Team, 2022). Two maps are provided for each concept so that the data can be viewed in two ways: synchronically and diachronically. Shared lexical items between adjacently spoken languages symbolize a synchronic picture of language contact. On the other hand, disparate terms among neighboring languages, coupled with similar terminology across long distances, may indicate a more diachronic depiction of either trade and exchange networks or even migration patterns.

From there, I estimated the domestication of each species as situated temporally and geographically in BR. For this, I actively consulted extra-linguistic sources. I compared the most up-to-date publications that I could find in the domains of archeology, history, and genetics with the linguistic findings as described in the following section which provides the results of this preliminary study.

4 Results

In the original study, by employing computationally supported methods that gave rise to the present one, we identified lexemes corresponding to the concepts MILLET, MAIZE, and CASSAVA to be shared among unrelated languages. To these, I added words for FONIO, SORGHUM, OKRA, RICE, YAM, and GROUND-NUT to the current study for the purposes of further investigating whether loan words for crops proliferated BR languages' lexica. Indeed, as is illustrated below, the same methods indicate a strong probability of shared vocabulary for these items among unrelated languages. In instances where the direction of borrowing is unclear, I describe the patterns as simply 'shared' rather than 'borrowed' from one group of speakers to another.

I treat each species individually in following subsections. First, comparative lexical patterns are presented, followed by extra-linguistic data, before depicting possible contact scenarios. As noted in the previous section, data are presented in the form of maps as well as tables. Each map in the article displays BR as an excerpt from *Wanderwords* which in some cases are spread across West Africa. Lexemes given in their 'form' (see Table 2 and discussion in Section 3.1

MAP 4 MILLET IN BR

above) and are grouped by common phonetic (sometimes phonemic) codes. Languages are listed along with their genealogical grouping.

4.1 MILLET ‘pearl millet’ *Pennisetum glaucum*¹¹

The first species to be treated here, appropriately given that it is the earliest African domesticate and nearly native to BR, is pearl millet.

4.1.1 Linguistic

Lexemes for MILLET in BR at first appear to be varied, with Bangime attesting a unique term, not shared with its closest Bozo-speaking neighbors, nor with West Dogon speakers. All Dogon languages spoken east of the city of Bandiagara, on the other hand, seem to be consistent in sharing a common form. Map 4 displays the lexemes found along the Bandiagara Escarpment.

Beginning with the language isolate Bangime, comparative terms for MILLET with several Bozo (Mande) languages are shown in Table 3.

Interestingly, by viewing the location of where these languages are spoken today in the larger version of Map 4 provided with the supplemental materials (<https://osf.io/8jkgx/>) we see that the Bozo variety which attests a form that appears most similar to that of Bangime, Kotya, is actually spoken across the Niger River to the west of where Bangime is spoken today. It would seem as if the form from neighboring Jenaama has had no impact on the Bangime lexeme. However, by comparing the word from Pondori, a Bozo variety which is spoken in the environs of the city of Djenné, we see that the word for MILLET in the Bozo language group is actually a compound of two nouns. The second noun of the compound corresponds to SEED among the Bozo languages.

11 Otherwise known as *Cenchrus americanus*.

TABLE 3 Bangime lexical source for MILLET among Bozo languages

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
dé-mè	pearl millet; (dèj = grain, seed)	Bangime	Isolate
dʒɛŋ	millet	Kotya	Soninke-Bozo
dʒʸɛ	millet; (pij = grain, seed)	Tieyaxo	Soninke-Bozo
dʒɛ pi	millet	Pondori	Soninke-Bozo
pi	millet	Korondougou	Soninke-Bozo
pi	millet (pearl millet); grain, seed	Jenaama	Soninke-Bozo
dégē	grass sp. / poacée sp.	Jenaama	Soninke-Bozo

In Bangime, the suffix which follows the lexical root for MILLET is frozen to many flora and fauna species.¹² The root *dèj* without its suffix simply refers to any grain or seed. In turn, these Bozo and Bangime varieties may additionally be compared to the word *dégē* in the Bozo Jenaama language, which is glossed as ‘grass sp. / poacée sp.’. Although RefLex also lists **dé* as a Proto-Bantu reconstruction for ‘millet, eleusine’, in fact, this form is only attested in the J and M zones which correspond to locations in Central-East Africa. Hence, an additional strong resemblance to a closer, Western Mande, language, Seenku is *dên* ~ *dɛ̃*, as compares to Bangime with the meaning ‘(single) grain, seed, nut’. These co-lexifications and similarities at great geographical distances could be evidence of the word’s shared contact history, corresponding to its time depth.

I propose that the origin of the complete compound which today refers to MILLET among Bozo (Mande) languages was likely ‘grass-seed’. Note further along comments regarding terms for FONIO follow a similar pattern.

Moving now onto the next lexeme found among BR languages, intriguingly, though the form differs, the Dogon languages which immediately neighbor Bangime in surrounding West Dogon languages, spoken in the southwestern area of the Escarpment, conflate the terms for ‘pearl millet’ and ‘(single) grain, seed, nut’. Examples in Table 4 illustrate the West Dogon forms plus possible connections with other languages of the area.

12 This suffix also occurs on language names, including [*bàngì-mé*]; it relates to the diminutive, the sole productive nominal suffix in the language. As will become relevant below, in Soninke, many animate nouns, including persons, plants, and ethnicities, end in a sequence [*me*]; the Bozo Jenaama cognate is [*-lèw̃*], plural [*-bē*].

TABLE 4 Terms for MILLET and SEED among West Dogon, Gur, and Mande languages

‘pearl millet’	‘(single) grain, seed, nut’	Language	Group
sê-j	sê-ǰ, sê-ǰ=gé	Ampari	West Dogon
sée-ŋgè	sèè	Bunoge	West Dogon
sée-ŋgè	síí	Mombo	West Dogon
sèè-ŋgè	sèè	Penange	West Dogon
sée-ŋgè	sée, sé-ŋgé	Tiranige Diga	West Dogon
ƴòò	ǰí	Senufo	Senufo (Gur?)
ǰí	bíó (‘baby’)	Tiefo	Gur
(sà) ǰó	sí	Bambara	East-Manding

Discussed in detail below, pearl millet is foundational to BR agricultural societies. The fundamental nature of pearl millet expressed simultaneously as a seed speaks to the concept’s profound depth in the language. Among the West Dogon languages, the link between the concepts MILLET and SEED is clear, however, there is additional evidence that these forms may be able to be traced to other languages spoken in modern-day Mali and neighboring Burkina Faso. That is, we see in Senufo, a language that is said to form part of the Gur group to which Tiefo belongs, easily relatable forms are found for SEED on the one hand and MILLET on the other. Additionally, as discussed in detail as follows, although MILLET is a different form in the Mande language Bambara which is widely found across many West African languages, the resemblance between the Dogon varieties – especially Mombo – to Bambara speakers’ form for SEED is striking.

By examining the extended version of Map 4 in the supplemental materials, we see that the most closely related Mande language to Bozo, Soninke, attests a completely different lexeme. The origin of the Soninke word for MILLET has been attributed to the unrelated but geographically proximate Berber group (Portères, 1959a). Lexical comparisons are shown in Table 5.

While the Soninke form for MILLET, and possibly some other Mande languages such as that shown for Bisa, has a clear association to the Berber languages with whom Soninke speakers are in close contact today, analysis from Kossmann (2020) shows that this connection must have followed the sound change from *NL (witnessed in Table 7 in the Tamasheq word) to LL as attested in these western Berber languages shown in the table and accompanying map.

TABLE 5 Berber origin for Soninke MILLET lexemes

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
e-næle	millet	Tamasheq	Berber
i-llan	millet	Taghzut	Berber
i-ʔlli	millet	Zenaga	Berber
jillé	mil	Soninke	Soninke-Bozo
j̄r	petit mil	Bisa	Eastern-Mande

Additionally, although Portères (1959a) claims that Songhay also draws an eventual source from Berber languages, this study finds the evidence less persuasive than that of the Berber-Soninke connection. Rather, the source of the Songhay form is more transparently connected to another branch of the Afro-Asiatic phylum: forms for MILLET from Chadic languages currently spoken in Chad are compared with those from Songhay languages in Table 6.

It would be tempting to suggest that the Songhay words are also composed of compounds formed from the word for MILLET in Chadic languages plus the final component *no* as found in the Songhay spoken in Hombori. Indeed, as illustrated below, languages with words for MILLET with the form *nɔ* are the most prevalent throughout West Africa. However, the final vowel among the Songhay lexemes represents the definite singular suffix and thus *no* is not a word in and of itself. And yet, the connection between Songhay and Chadic languages is evident without a clear direction of transfer. For Central Chadic, Gravina (2014) reconstructs **hiji* for eight groups across 14 Chadic languages with reflexes such as those shown in Table 6. The Songhay languages in the database also show robust dispersal.

The fourth lexeme for MILLET shown in Map 4 which is so widely spread across the eastern edges of the Escarpment is, at its source, proposed to be a product of the Mande expansion discussed in Section 2.2 above. Speakers of the *linguae francae* Bambara in Mali, and closely related Jula in Ivory Coast and Burkina Faso, are the likely propagators. Strikingly similar examples of words for MILLET range not only across eastern Dogon languages, but also follow a longitudinal line all the way to the southern coast of West Africa. Comparative lexemes coded in RefLex as *nɔ* are illustrated in Table 7 and on Map 5.

Note that there is but one Dogon language – Tebul Ure – with a form which can be coded as *nɔ*. Other Dogon languages, such as Najamba, pattern with West Manding languages as illustrated in Table 9 below.

TABLE 6 Chadic correspondences with Songhay MILLET lexemes

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
hàjnò	cultivated millet	Humburi Senni	Eastern Songhay
hááni	mil (gros)	Dendi	Eastern Songhay
hèèni	petit mil, <i>pennicetum typhoides</i> (graminées)	Kaado	Eastern Songhay
hèjni	mil	Kaado (Ayorou-Goungokore)	Eastern Songhay
haaj	millet / mil	Ouldeme	Chadic
haj	millet	Moloko	Chadic

TABLE 7 MILLET and GRAIN lexical similarities across geographically eastern and southern languages of West and Western Africa

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
(sà) ɲó	(pearl) millet	Bambara	East-Manding
(sà) ɲó	(pearl) millet	Jula	East-Manding
ɲɔ	dolo (millet beer)	San	East-Manding
ɲǎ	millet or sorghum	Koro	East-Manding
ɲó	pearl millet	Tebul Ure	North-Plateau Dogon
ɲɔ̄	millet	Abé	Kwa
ɲɲǎ	millet	Krobu	Kwa
ɲɔ́	millet	Bété	Kru
ɲɔ́	millet	Godié	Kru
ɲɔ́	millet	Ega	Benue-Congo
ɲó	grain	Yrewe	Kru

Map 5 actually shows that the majority of Western African languages of the central and southern zones, especially those spoken in areas where pearl millet is prevented from growing today due to climatic conditions, use a term that completely differs from that of the proposed Berber form found in Soninke, or the word that is shared between Bangime and Bozo varieties. It is clear that the form for MILLET coded as *ɲJO* is a loanword spread to these languages through their speakers' trade networks.

MAP 5 MILLET coded as *ɲo* across unrelated languages

Map 5 further demonstrates a distribution in phonetic variation that is more geographic than genealogical. Comparative lexemes in Tables 7–9 show that, in addition to the form given above with a palatal glide [j] or nasal [ɲ] followed by a mid back [-ATR] vowel [ɔ], two additional lexemes attest either the mid back [+ATR] counterpart [o] or a high back vowel [u] ~ [ʊ] (of both) [+/-ATR] specifications. The phonetic similarities are shared across language families, but often in geographically proximate areas, suggesting some cases of close contact among speakers of unrelated languages.

Somewhat less common as a lexical stem among Mande languages, but frequently found among compounds (see the supplemental materials and comments below regarding MAIZE), is the form for, or related to, MILLET as *ɲo*.¹³ Some examples are demonstrated in Table 8.

Rather, the majority of Dogon languages with similar forms begin with a palatal glide and a high back vowel. The phonetically closest forms are found among languages which are actually spoken several hundred kilometers directly south of the Bandiagara Escarpment. Yet, without language contact, this phonetic variation is otherwise difficult to support from Dogon-internal variation as both back vowel heights are found in open syllables following palatals.

Although it is reasonable to posit a common Mande language loan as the source for these widespread terms for MILLET across disparate languages, unfortunately, as of yet, there are no reconstructions for ‘pearl millet’ from Proto-Mande, at least as far as those proposed by Kastenholz (1996). For the

13 Again, while Gur languages have yet to be fully integrated into the comparative dataset, the Proto-Central Gur reconstruction for MILLET is **ɲa* (Manessy, 1979: 104).

TABLE 8 MILLET lexical similarities across languages currently spoken in western and southern portions of West Africa

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
jó-gé	pearl millet	Bondu So	North-Plateau Dogon
jò	millet or sorghum	Khassonké	West-Manding
jòò	millet	Mandinka	West-Manding
dʒo ŋo	mil	Hainyaxo	Soninke-Bozo
jo	millet	Aizi	Kru

TABLE 9 MILLET lexical similarities across languages currently spoken in western and southern portions of West Africa

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
jū	millet (grain crop, <i>Cenchrus spicatus</i>)	Jalkunan	Manding-Jogo
jú	pearl millet	Toru Tegu	Escarpment Dogon
júù	pearl millet	Nanga	Nangan Dogon
júú	pearl millet	Jamsay	Plains Dogon
jàjòó	millet	Agni	Kwa

South-Western Mande branch, Vydrin (2009) lists *jɔ, which is certainly broadly attested throughout the languages of that branch and beyond the Mande language family as shown in Table 7 above. Recall that we also saw that the Soninke-Bozo branch of the Mande language group employs different forms, with the explanation for the discrepancy in Soninke at least being that the divergent form is a probable loan word from Berber speakers. Thus, to understand more about the spread of pearl millet and its nomenclature, we turn now to interdisciplinary sources.

4.1.2 Extra-linguistic

Archeological evidence supports pearl millet cultivation as representing the beginnings of Sub-Saharan Africa agriculture (Ozainne et al., 2014). Pearl millet (*Cenchrus americanus*, previously known as *Pennisetum glaucum*) is the most ancient dated West African grain, and its provenance is attributed to an area north of BR (Burgarella et al., 2018; Manning et al., 2011; Fuller et al., 2021). Manning et al. (2011) have located evidence of domesticated pearl millet in the Niger

MAP 6 Pearl millet domestication and dispersal from Fuller et al. (2021); dates are indicated in median age BC/AD format

River bend, at the site indicated as Er Negf in Figure 1 and Map 6 above, dating back to around 4,500 years ago.

Recently revised methods and analysis using electron microscopy of pottery sherds found in the north of Mali may even push the date of pearl millet domestication back much further in time (Fuller et al., 2021). Burgarella et al. (2018) used whole-genome sequencing data of both wild and cultivated pearl millet from areas in Mali and Mauritania to form a model of the time depth and location of the plant's first domestication. Their findings support the archeological results, while their model suggests a western and southern dispersal of pearl millet to Mauritania and the Niger River bend. Map 6 demonstrates geographical points where evidence for the first domestication of millet has been found in and near BR.

In the present-day West African climate, pearl millet is a staple crop which is grown in regions from Senegal in the west to Chad in the east, and into Burkina Faso and Guinea (Rhoné et al., 2020). Among BR populations, pearl millet is an essential grain upon which the majority of meals are based. From its origin in what is now Saharan-West African, theories differ as to whether pearl millet as a cultivated grain was spread widely or was domesticated at distinctive sites independently. Winchell et al. (2018) argue that pearl millet was not fully domesticated by the time it reached Sudan, around 3000 years ago, which falls in line with their estimates for early sorghum domestication as discussed below. Kevin, Manning and Champion (2017) in their overview of evidence pertaining to the spread of pearl millet, discuss corridors from northern to central Mali in 2500 and 2000 BCE, two in Mauritania to Senegal taking place from 1750–1500 BCE and 1900–1500 BCE respectively, and then to northern Ghana by ca. 2000 BCE. The linguistic evidence provided here suggests – at least – five distinct lexemes for pearl millet from the languages presently spoken in BR.

Accordingly, if there was one sole point of origin, it would be somewhat surprising that terms for pearl millet among languages currently spoken in an area so close to the grain's prurupted domestication are so varied. On the other hand, given the pearl millet's deep time depth, linguistic variation is indeed expected.

Songhay peoples currently occupy the location where evidence for the first domestication of pearl millet was found, near the modern city of Gao. Yet, evidence of Songhay occupation of Gao dates back only to around 1400 years ago. Souag (2012) discusses linguistic data that does indicate Proto-Songhay speakers practiced agriculture. Today, the term for MILLET among closely related Songhay languages attests contact with speakers of Chadic languages spoken to the far east in today's country of Chad where, at Lake Chad, the earliest pearl millet seeds have been dated to around 3000 years ago (Fuller et al., 2021). Because both groups show proliferation of a common form, the direction of the loan is indeterminate, though the age of the grain among Proto-Chadic speakers allude to the source being therein.

In terms of alternative initial ethno-linguistic groups, historians attribute the domestication of pearl millet to Proto-Soninke (Kea, 2004) or Proto-Mande (Brooks, 1986) speakers. Brooks (1986: 48) states,

Groups living in the southern Sahara along the receding shorelines of shallow lakes intensified their collection of wild grains and began to cultivate some of them. These included proto-Mande speakers in the Tichit area of present-day Mauretania who cultivated millet sometime after 2000 B.C. and other groups to the east (proto-Nilo-Saharan speakers?) who domesticated sorghum.

Based on glotto-chronological estimates Vydrin (2009) posits that Proto-Mande was spoken around the second half of the 4th millennium BC in the area where Mauritania is today, with Proto-Soninke-Bozo and other subgroups beginning to split off about 2100 BC. (2009: 115) places the latter date to coincide with the founding of agricultural practices along valleys of the Niger River such as those that lead into BR. Although Brooks makes a distinction, linguistically, Soninke is currently classified as being a Mande language.

The only form that has been reconstructed to any branch of Mande, **ɲo* for the South-Western Mande branch, is also the form that is the most widely dispersed throughout West Africa. This lexeme which is so pervasive across West Africa with a likely Western Mande source was probably proliferated by those who traded along networks west to the Atlantic coast as well as south along the Niger River, from its bend to its delta. As noted in the Section 2.2 above, the so-called "Mande Expansion" first involved merchants before their encompass-

4000–3000	2500–2000	2100–1725	1150–1100
Proto-Mande	Western Mande split	Soninke-Bozo split	Pre-Dogon
Southern Saharan homeland	Sahel	Niger River	Ounjougou
Pre-farming	Early millet farming	Early millet and rice farming	Early millet and rice farming

FIGURE 8 Early Mande peoples' transition to farming timeline (YBP)

ing rule over the area through powerful Mande empires. A proposed timeline incorporating dates and Mande language reconstructions from Vydrin (2009) is provided in Figure 8.

According to Vydrin's timeline, Proto-Mande speakers would fall into pre-farming populations. Indeed, terms for MILLET are varied among Mande languages today, suggesting that pearl millet farming took place after the linguistic group's branches began to split. For instance, as discussed above, the word for pearl millet in Soninke is a likely later loan from Berber speakers who live in today's northern Mali and Mauritania. The trajectory for this loan, as noted in the previous subsection, is based on the fact that, if the form for MILLET found in Soninke was borrowed from Berber, it would not have been at the stage of Proto-Berber, evidenced by an innovation that occurred after the branches had split. Additionally, although Chaker (2010) argues for the antiquity of Berber lexemes for MILLET, Kossmann (2020) states that Proto-Berber is a relatively recent family, estimated at about (600 BCE). Early links between Soninke and Berber speakers are certainly supported by archaeological, as well as cultural, evidence (MacDonald, 1996). Thus, the historical attribution of primary pearl millet cultivation to Proto-Soninke (via Proto-Berber) speakers is, at least linguistically, unfounded.

As pertains to the Bandiagara Escarpment, dates for first pearl millet domestication have a median estimated date of 1725 BC at Ounjougou. This time period would fall within the time when "pre-Dogon" populations of which Mayor et al. (2005) speak as being a cultural "mosaic" occupied the Bandiagara escarpment. It is also around this time (between 1150 and 1100 BC), further following Vydrin (2009: 115), that the Bozo languages are thought to have separated from Soninke. Groups presently farming along the western sides of the Escarpment where the Niger River floods valleys during the rainy season, speakers of Bangime and Bozo, as well as today's southwestern Dogon, must have been geographically isolated enough – or practicing pearl millet farming early

enough – from other Mande speakers to establish their own word for pearl millet which was resistant to replacement from groups with whom they would later be in contact.

As shown among the maps above, Bozo languages are still spoken along the Niger River and its valleys, including the valley that ends at the cliff where Bangime and the West Dogon languages are spoken today. Lexical evidence shown above illustrates that Bangime exclusively shares a lexeme for MILLET with Bozo languages, suggesting an interval of contact that preceded neighboring Dogon speakers' current positions. That is, any apparent Dogon language influence on Bangime would have followed that of Bozo, which aligns with the notion of a pre-Dogon occupation of the Bandiagara Escarpment.

4.1.3 Summary

Although there are five different lexical roots for MILLET found in the relative area where evidence of the first domestication of pearl millet has been found, one is widely spread throughout unrelated and geographically disparate ethnolinguistic groups. It is proposed that Mande speakers spread the term *ɲo* – with reflexes attesting some vocalic and consonantal variation – across West Africa during the Mande Expansion. Some Dogon speakers were affected by this spread, while others retained an estimated earlier term that is co-lexified with SEED. Today's Songhay languages employ a term that closely resembles that of Chadic languages *haj*. Like West Dogon groups, Bangime, and Bozo languages also use the same lexemes for MILLET and SEED, though the terms differ: *see* in the former and *de* in the latter. Gur groups apparently also share the former form as do some other languages of the Mande group. The Bangime-Bozo connection was at first obscured because the original term for MILLET was a compound likely composed of the concepts SEED and GRASS. Several other language groups of the alleged Niger-Congo language phylum share a form which is similar to SEED/MILLET in the West Dogon languages suggesting that this may be the primary form in the area.

Based on the linguistic as well as the extra-linguistic evidence, it appears that Proto-Mande speakers began farming practices using pearl millet before either Berber or Songhay-speaking groups came to settle in areas where evidence for primary pearl millet cultivation has been found such as Er Negf and Karkarichinkat.

Bangime and Bozo speakers were probably farming pearl millet at a time and/or place prior to either population's encountering today's neighboring Dogon speakers, but following Bozo speakers' split with their Mande ancestors. Eastern Dogon groups' encounters with pearl millet were heavily influenced by the Mande Expansion through Western Mande languages, while West Dogon

speakers retain an older word for pearl millet shared with potentially distantly related languages that also signifies a simple seed or grain.

Given the importance of pearl millet to BR communities, it is unlikely that a word was lost and replaced with a loan word in the Dogon languages that seem to share the form with Western Mande and so many other unrelated languages of West Africa, yet the example of RICE shown below could present a counter-example to the relationship between a crop's importance and its borrowability. As an African example outside of the region, Bostoen (2007) demonstrates how easily terms for pearl millet are transferred to other domesticated plant grains among Bantu languages and beyond. This study finds similar results with respect to FONIO, SORGHUM, and MAIZE as detailed as follows.

4.2 FONIO 'fonio' *Digitaria exilis*

In contrast to lexemes for MILLET, those for FONIO among BR languages are quite uniform, nevertheless with variation in line with a layer time depth. As with pearl millet, Portères (1959a: 78) argues that words for 'fonio' have their roots in the word for 'seed' in Dogon and Bambara, and 'food' generally among other West African languages. This study is in accordance with Portères' suggestion that for FONIO and MILLET lexemes among languages in the database are synonymous with SEED and FOOD, but the link is not straightforward and requires explanation as provided in the following subsection.

4.2.1 Linguistic

Map 7 shows mostly homogenous terms for FONIO are attested throughout BR save for the forms in Bangime, Fulfulde (the Atlantic language pictured in the map), and Songhay.

Table 10 illustrates that the Dogon language forms shown in the excerpt of BR languages provided in Map 7 can be compared to Mande as well as other unrelated Atlantic languages spoken today at great geographical distances in West Africa.

In contrast to the case of MILLET, the word for FONIO in the modern Bozo language Jenaama closely aligns with forms found in today's Dogon languages. Additionally, although apparent sound changes would have had to occur, languages spoken along the Atlantic coast of West Africa also attest a form for FONIO that contains the same broad phonetic code *PO(D)* as these Dogon and Mande languages spoken in BR.

In response to Portères' comments regarding lexical similarities between FONIO and FOOD, note that, in Jenaama Bozo, the lexeme for FONIO *pùwǔ*, is identical to that for MEAL in Bangime *pòw̃* ~ *pùwǔ*. Furthermore, *fǔjǔ* in Bambara is translated as 'couscous de fonio' whereas *fǔnǔ* is the grain, '*Digitaria exilis*,

MAP 7 FONIO in BR

TABLE 10 Comparative Dogon, Mande, and Atlantic lexemes for FONIO coded as PO(D)

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
pùwǔ	fonio (grain)	Jenaama	Soninke-Bozo
pǔǔ	fonio	Tommo So	Escarpment Dogon
pǔǔ	fonio	Togo Kan	Plains Dogon
pǔǔ-ɲgè	fonio	Penange	West Dogon
pǔǔ-ɲgǔ	fonio	Najamba	North-Plateau Dogon
ε-bɔɔɲa	petit mil, fonio	Kujamutay	Jóola (Atlantic-Bak)
pǔdè	fonio fonio	Zialo	Western Mande
foɲɲe	fonio (<i>Digitaria exilis</i>)	Pular	North Atlantic
foɲno	<i>Digitaris, exilis</i> , millet, fonio	Sereer	North Atlantic
fɔɲanɲo	fonio	Soninke	Soninke-Bozo

fonio, *éleusine*.¹⁴ Also note the similarity of the forms for FONIO such as that of the Atlantic language Pular *foɲno* to the words for MILLET provided in the previous section. That is, a compound composed of something similar to **fɔwɔ-*

14 Incidentally, the term used in English and French, *fonio*, clearly has its source ultimately in West Africa.

TABLE 11 Comparative lexemes among unrelated, non-neighboring languages for FONIO coded as PI(D)

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
wī-bè	fonio	Bangime	Isolate
pi	fonio	San	East-Manding
fɪ́ɲí	Digitaria exilis, fonio, éleusine	Bambara	East-Manding
pindi	fonio	Nalu	North Atlantic
fɪ̀ndi	fonio (en grains)	Balante	Atlantic-Bak
fɪ̀ndi	fonio	Mandinka	West-Manding
ɛ-fundɔ	fonio	Gusilay	Jóola (Atlantic-Bak)

100 MEAL-MILLET can be imagined to have meant a prepared meal of fonio grains.¹⁵ Over time, the meaning could easily have shifted to a different crop. These changes point to fonio's integration into the lexica of these languages and of its meal's importance to its speakers.

We now move on to explore the form found in Bangime before turning to that of Songhay. By viewing the expanded version of Map 7 and examining comparative forms in Table 11 from languages that are spoken at great geographic distances to BR, we find possible similarities among languages in the Mande, as well as Gur and Atlantic, groupings.

In fact, in Table 11, we find further evidence in support of Portères' statement that lexemes for 'fonio' and 'seed' are the same in Dogon and Mande languages. By comparing forms for SEED/MILLET shown above from Bozo languages in Section 4.1.1 with lexemes for FONIO in Table 11, we see that both are indeed coded as PI(D). Among these forms, the (D) is provided in parentheses because, as is explained below, stems with nasalization on final vowels and/or sonorants are inferred to have lost either the nasal or stop segment.

That is, in Bangime, as well as the Dogon languages as was illustrated for MILLET and shown here for FONIO, [f] is not part of the phonetic inventory. Loan words that are integrated into these languages are realized through bilabial realizations of other manners of articulation such as from /f/ to [p] or [w]. Additionally, note that the suffix which appears on the Bangime lexeme,

15 Portères (1959:308) also interprets *fo-nio* as being a compound involving 'millet' (he considers the root to simply mean 'cereal', but he glosses *fo* as 'thing').

-be, is the only productive suffix to appear on nouns in the language. Its allomorph *-mɛ* was mentioned in the previous subsection as being associated with many plant and animal species including MILLET above and RICE below (also the name of the language itself). In further support of its being a loan, word-initial *w* is rare in Bangime; in the lexicon, the glide only appears as an onset to prevent words which begin with back vowels as appearing in word-initial position.

It was also shown in the previous subsection that among many Bozo varieties compounds of MILLET (GRASS)-SEED became reduced to simply SEED and then shifted in today's languages to mean MILLET. In a parallel manner in Bangime, I propose that the word for SEED in Bangime [*dé*] is the root of the derived form for MILLET [*dé-mè*], and that this root is shared between Bozo languages. Thus, the root of the lexeme for FONIO [*wū*], if indeed related to PI(D), is also the product of a shared semantic shift from SEED, as relates to the other portion of the nominal compound found among the Bozo languages.

However, this shared contact event between Bangime speakers and those of the Bozo languages from the Mande group would have to have taken place prior to a sound change that now distinguishes related Bozo varieties and East-Manding languages such as Bambara. That is, word-initial [p] is permitted in Bangime, but words with an initial [w] are rare, as noted the glide is mostly limited to otherwise illicit word-initial onsetless syllables with back vowels. Thus, the source of the lexeme for FONIO in Bangime was either directly derived from a different word with an actual [w] – consider *fomw* ~ *fomba* for FONIO in the Gur language Turka – or another word entirely such as those for SEED.¹⁶

Excluding the form in Bangime, Blench (2016) suggests that words for FONIO such as those shown in Tables 13–14 for the Dogon, Mande, and even Songhay all come from a common form which he posits as **fundí*, with its source in West Mande. Although the West Mande language Khassonké does actually attest *fúndí* today, the majority of the Mande languages, with examples shown in Table 10, contain mid back vowels. In Table 10, these forms are separately codified as PO(D). Blench (2016: 5) does not distinguish the various forms found among the Dogon languages, simply listing “Dogon” as *põ*. In fact, as exemplified by the Tommo So form *pɔ̀ɔ̀*, the vowel is a [-ATR] [ɔ], with cognates of differing length and tone throughout the Dogon languages, though the nasalization is consistent. Again, the accommodation of /f/ to [p] among Dogon

16 The only Mande reconstruction available for ‘seed’ is **wɛla*, from Proto-Eastern Mande (Schreiber, 2008). He also reconstructs ‘meal’ (see above) as **pɔ.be-le*. Further comparative forms with Bangime will be explored in forthcoming publications.

TABLE 12 Comparative lexemes among unrelated, non-neighboring languages for FONIO coded as PI(G)

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
fɪŋgì	cultivated fonio (grain)	Tondi Kiini	Eastern Songhay
peŋg-	fonio (<i>Digitaria exilis</i>)	Koromfé	Gur
fóŋgí	fonio	Natorio	Gur
míníŋ / bíníŋ (wìndì)	fonio récolter le fonio	Kpele de Guinée Kaado	Western Mande Eastern Songhay

languages is expected as the fricative phoneme does not exist in any of the Dogon languages.

Nevertheless, I am in accordance with Blench's findings that a relationship exists between the PI(D) and PO(D) forms. Phonologically, as vowel harmony is a common feature of West African languages in general, a final front vowel could spread its features throughout the word causing forms such as Khassonké *fúndí* to become *findí*, such as is witnessed in the closely related Mande language Mandinka. The discrepancy here is in the forms that end with *-ndV* and those that do not. Furthermore, in Table 12, additional forms for FONIO are provided that resemble the Songhay word illustrated on Map 7 above.

I interpret the common ending that occurs among many of these languages' comparative lexemes, *-ngV ~ -ndV*, as a noun class suffix from the Atlantic (or Gur) group. The origin of the word FONIO across most of West Africa is therefore probably derived from a root composed of a bilabial consonant plus a back vowel, something like *PO*, which likely had a more general meaning such as MEAL or SEED as presented above.

The final forms to be discussed here for FONIO are shown in Table 13. The lexeme from Humburi Senni Songhay *sérémbò* strongly resembles that of the Atlantic language Fulfulde *serembe* (which is itself a likely loan and semantic shift from the Dogon languages' word for SORGHUM as illustrated below). Shown in Table 13, the form in the Songhay language Dendi *háŋtáájà* is similar to one of the Soninke variants *húnáŋgè*.

These FONIO forms, with the addition of the example from Songhay Tondi Kiini above, show that Songhay languages attest shared words with three different sources: Mande, Soninke, and Fulfulde. In turn, the form in the Macina variety of Fulfulde is clearly connected to the Dogon languages' word for SORGHUM

TABLE 13 Lexical sources for FONIO in Songhay languages

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
háŋtáájà	fonio	Dendi	Eastern Songhay
hújánŋè	fonio	Soninke	Soninke-Bozo
sérémbò	fonio (cultivated grain)	Humburi Senni	Eastern Songhay
seremmbè	fonio	Macina Fulfulde	North Atlantic

(and MAIZE) as illustrated in the following subsection. For these languages' speakers (as was the case for pearl millet), fonio was apparently not acquired as part of the expansion of Mande-speaking people and trade took place through separate networks.

Curiously, even though Blench (2016) argues for a domestication of fonio in the "Guinea/Mali region", and that this was the primary nucleus of diversification based on linguistic evidence such as that provided here, external findings as presented in the next sub-subsection argue for a recent introduction of the grain, at least to BR.

4.2.2 Extra-linguistic

In terms of the grain's providence, Purseglove (1985) actually attributes the initial domestication of fonio to over 5000 years ago in the Inner Niger Delta of what is now located in central Mali. More recent research by Ozainne et al. (2014) presents dates from a much later period – only 1600–2800 years ago. As pertains to the presence of sorghum in BR, and then fonio, *ibid.* (2014: 366) reference,

In fact, in the Niger Inland Delta in Mali ... fonio (*Digitaria exilis*) appears from 400 cal AD (McIntosh, 1995), although the latter has been mentioned in contexts dated around 800 cal BC.

TAKEZAWA and CISSE, 2004

Excavations at Tongo Maaré Diabal, a site located near today's city of Douentza located at the northwestern tip of the Bandiagara Escarpment, and Sadia, on the Seno Plains to the east of the Escarpment, find a predominance of pearl millet until about 1000 years ago when other crops, including fonio, were introduced (Champion and Gestrich et al., 2021; Champion and Fuller et al., 2021). Champion (2020) explicitly disagrees with Blench's postulation that fonio is indigenous to Mali based on its widespread common linguistic forms.

He argues that the absence of fonio grains from Neolithic and Iron Age West African archeological sites suggests that its introduction into modern-day Mali occurred during the era of urbanization.¹⁷

4.2.3 Summary

Somewhat surprising given the lack of archeological evidence, this study does find linguistic support for fonio as being a crop that is deeply rooted into BR languages' lexica, thus suggesting its early integration. While Blench states in a footnote (pg. 4) that fonio remains important to the Dogon, Heath (2007) clarifies that fonio was formerly widely cultivated across the Bandiagara Escarpment, but is now absent from northern Dogon areas and is only sparsely used by the Dogon in the central and southern parts of the Escarpment.

Geographically, forms with the code PI(D) are dispersed from the interior of West Africa, all the way from Atlantic coast, and to the western edge of BR. I propose that the original form for PI(D) reflexes could have been something similar to what Blench suggests, i.e. **fu-ndi*. And while the root of this lexeme's source is likely linked to Mande traders, these must have been Mande-language speakers who lived, or at least were in contact with, speakers who inhabited the Atlantic coast. The suffix *-ndi* is a productive Atlantic language noun class suffix associated with organic substances and mass nouns, including, in Fulfulde, pearl millet (Pozdniakov, 2022: 227). As in the case of MILLET, Mande traders were likely to have propagated terms for FONIO via their expansion across West Africa.

One way of reconciling these competing archeological and linguistic scenarios for the early appearance of the domesticated fonio grain is to suggest that fonio was indeed cultivated by early West Africans, but in an area outside the scope of archeologically investigated areas. That is, the linguistic evidence indicates that the lexemes for FONIO are deeply dispersed among West African languages generally, and that the meaning of the form for FONIO is as basic as SEED or MEAL. Specifically in BR, words for FONIO were borrowed from Mande languages into Dogon languages and Bangime before the settlement of the Escarpment, and subsequent dispersal, throughout the Escarpment, as the forms are quite uniform throughout, unlike the patterns witnessed for MILLET. Whereas pearl millet grains and lexemes were obtained by at least eastern Dogon groups through exchange with Mande traders during the second phase of the Mande Expansion, fonio represents an even more basic subsistence for

17 However, he also states, "Fonio (*Digitaria exilis*) might have been locally domesticated in the Inland Niger Delta or adjacent region as a crop that could take advantage of marginal soils" (Champion and Gestrich et al., 2021: 7).

TABLE 14 SORGHUM lexeme shared among Bangime, Mande, and West Dogon languages

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
ẽĩndzè	Sorghum bicolor	Bangime	Isolate
kenige	sorgho	Soninke	Soninke-Bozo
kénìgé	Sorghum bicolor	Bambara	East Manding
síĩndzà	Sorghum bicolor	Bunoge	West Dogon
sĩndzàá-ŋgè	Sorghum bicolor	Penange	West Dogon

Words for SORGHUM among the Mande languages in the sample are more cohesive than those for MILLET. Additionally, the geographic distribution of the Dogon languages is important. Similar to the case of MILLET, with a few exceptions, Dogon languages spoken on the eastern side of the Bandiagara Escarpment form a cohesive, yet separate, group. In contrast to lexemes for MILLET or FONIO, though, is the similarity Bangime bears to its closest neighboring Dogon speakers.

Bangime shares a form for SORGHUM with Soninke, Bambara, and West Dogon languages as shown in the expanded version of Map 8 and the comparative Table 14 above. However, SORGHUM in the Bozo language closest to Bangime is *síjēw̃*, and thus, as with MILLET and FONIO, is not the primary Bozo nor Mande source for the Bangime lexeme.

Blench (2006) discusses the lexical root for SORGHUM which he codifies as *#kyi* as being one which is pervasive across West Africa. The Proto-Mande reconstruction for *Sorghum margaritifera* is **keNte* (Kastenholz, 1996). This lexical root is in line with that which we find in most Mande languages, as well as Bangime and some of the West Dogon languages. We even find, by expanding the extended version of Map 8, that such forms related to SORGHUM are found in other languages of the Mande family such as Vai, *kèndè-gbòfú* ‘a “bread” made from *Sorghum margaritifera*’ and unrelated Gbaya, *kédáfón*, ‘sweet variety of sorghum’. Tondi Kiini, the Songhay variety spoken closest to Nangan Dogon speakers, also attests *kèŋgòó* for ‘sorghum grain spike’, however all other Songhay lexemes for SORGHUM (including that of Tondi Kiini) consist of codified KAB with reflexes *hàmbó* and *hààmó*, suggesting that the Songhay form in Tondi Kiini is a loanword from neighboring Dogon languages.

Blench also states that the *#kyi* root was prolifically borrowed arguing, “sorghum cultivation spread well after the establishment of the main linguistic groups in West Africa” (Blench, 2006: 20). A caveat to this statement is that

TABLE 15 Comparative lexemes for SORGHUM in Dogon languages

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
èmà	Sorghum bicolor	Yanda Dom	North-Plateau
émbà	sorgho Sorghum bicolor	Mombo	West
émá	Sorghum bicolor	Tiranige	West
èmbá-ŋgó	Sorghum bicolor	Najamba	North-Plateau
èmé	Sorghum bicolor	Gourou	Plains
èmmé	Sorghum bicolor	Donno So	Escarpment
èèmbé	Sorghum bicolor	Nanga	Nangan
èmbé-j	Sorghum bicolor	Bankan Tey	Nangan

the Dogon languages were not considered in Blench's (2006) survey of comparative lexemes for SORGHUM. As illustrated in Table 15 above, there are two primary reflexes among the Dogon languages which can both be represented as one form codified as EB.

As was done for the above forms for MILLET, those for SORGHUM can be further divided based on their phonetic forms. The lexemes in Table 15 are collectively coded on the extended version of Map 8. This coding has reflexes which end in a final [ɛ] or [a]; compare Dogul Dom *émmè* with Ampari *émbà*. Note as well the [±ATR] counterparts for the stem-initial vowel [ɛ] and [e]. Furthermore, the sequence transcribed as mb in the second form, phonetically realized as prenasalization [ᵐb], is simplified to a singleton or geminate [m] in several Dogon languages.

In summary of the linguistic data from BR, SORGHUM lexemes are even more widely distributed across the Dogon languages than those for MILLET or FONIO. Yet, there remains a split between Dogon languages spoken on either side of the Bandiagara Escarpment – eastern and western – in particular the southwestern quadrant of the cliff as well as Bangime showing influence from Mande languages spoken just to the west of the Bandiagara Escarpment. The linguistic evidence would suggest a different domestication and dispersal trajectory for sorghum than that of pearl millet or fonio. We turn now to cross-disciplinary research.

4.3.2 Extra-linguistic

Indeed, in contrast to pearl millet, sorghum was not first domesticated in West Africa, but rather far to the east in modern-day Sudan, dated to between an estimated 3500–3000 BC (Winchell et al. 2018; Winchell et al., 2017). Intriguingly, Bostoen (2007a) shows convincing evidence for the Proto-East Bantu root for ‘pearl millet’ **bèdé* as being a lexical transfer from Nilotic languages’ term for sorghum. Similarly, lexemes for SORGHUM from Nilotic languages such as Luo (Dholuo), transcribed as both *béél* or *bél*, could be the primary source of the easterly Dogon languages’ terms. Naturally, the similarity between the Bantu forms that Bostoen has gathered through his fieldwork and those from the Nilotic languages he has found is much more striking than that between the Dogon languages above. However, given the time and distance these terms would have had to travel to arrive in BR, large sound changes are expected.

In terms of time depth in the BR, Ozainne et al. (2014) ascribe the presence of cultivated sorghum in the Niger Inland Delta of Mali to the end of the 1st millennium BC. At the site of Dia Shoma near modern-day Djenné, Arazi (2005: 338) notes,

This intriguing shift in staple grains [pearl millet and sorghum (*Sorghum bi-color*)] may indicate the arrival of newcomers [start of the second millennium AD (Horizon IV)], who according to oral traditions, might have been of Mande origins.

As presented above, Mande peoples have long been traders and merchants of ancient grains throughout West Africa.

Naturally, a distant point of origin does not preclude sorghum being separately domesticated in the western Sahelian regions, or its being dispersed across the continent by Mande traders and merchants. Today, along and atop the Bandiagara Escarpment, sorghum and pearl millet are usually grown together, with sorghum in the wetter parts of the fields. Like pearl millet, though to a lesser extent, sorghum is used for porridge and fermented for beer.

4.3.3 Summary

As in the case of MILLET, we see a lexical split for words for SORGHUM with an east-west divide between the languages spoken along, atop, and adjacent to the Escarpment. However, whereas with forms for MILLET the Mande influence was clearly concentrated on the eastern Bandiagara Dogon languages, here we see that the western Dogon languages more closely align with terms for SORGHUM from the west – from both Mande and Atlantic language groups. At least partially, the linguistic evidence aligns with data from across different

disciplines; an eastern origin of the sorghum grain is evidenced in the literature. Yet, additional linguistic data also indicate that West Dogon speakers likely obtained the grain and its name from Soninke or Bambara speakers who live not far from them today. Bangime uses a word that could have come from either Soninke or West Dogon peoples.

The other lexical root that is widespread throughout most of the Dogon languages probably represents an older form, however, the area where these Dogon languages is spoken has been dated as having a shift in material culture to that of the Dogon around 800 years ago. This suggests that, if the archeological evidence is correct in suggesting a longer presence of *SORGHUM* in the immediate area than that of *FONIO*, these Dogon populations were probably not the first to cultivate sorghum on the Escarpment.

These data suggest sorghum cultivation in BR follows that of millet and fonio, as crop names for sorghum mimic today's geographical locations, and thus were established after the settlement of the Escarpment. As shown in the following subsection, words for *SORGHUM* also appear in compounds indicating an imported crop, corn, or maize.

4.4 MAIZE 'corn' *Zea mays*

Maize, or corn, (*Zea mays*) is thought to be an imported crop from relatively recent times – brought to West Africa by Portuguese sailors in the 17th century (Miracle, 1965) – thus, non-native terms are expected. However, as outlined in the following sub-subsection, nearly all lexemes for *MAIZE* in BR are composed of compounds incorporating the terms for other cultivated plants that have been thus far presented in this article.

4.4.1 Linguistic

Terms for *MAIZE* in BR languages are compounds drawn from native vocabulary rather than loan words. The words are largely split between nouns composed of the lexemes for *SORGHUM*, but also some for *MILLET*. Additionally, as shown in Map 9, the geographical distribution of *MAIZE* lexemes mostly matches that of *SORGHUM*.

MAIZE in BR languages is composed of compounds using a mixture of native and loaned lexemes discussed in this paper, *SORGHUM*, but also *MILLET* and *OKRA*. Examples from Dogon languages include Donno So *sàmèmmé* and Gourou *pòròjúú* respectively. The first component of the Donno So compound corresponds to a meadow or grassland,¹⁹ while the first noun in the Gourou compound is the lexeme for *OKRA*,²⁰ discussed in further detail below.

19 The other noun of this compound *sáñà* could also mean to 'bird'.

20 The first noun of a compound in the Dogon languages always carries low tones.

MAP 9 MAIZE in BR

TABLE 16 Comparative compounds for SORGHUM across BR languages

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
birò n dɔ́	corn	Bangime	Isolate
bàrà èmbě-j	corn, maize	Bankan Tey	Nangan Dogon
bàr mě-ǰ	corn, maize	Ben Tey	Nangan Dogon
mbam mbaari	corn, maize	Fulfulde	North Atlantic
pòrò júú	corn, maize	Gourou	Plains Dogon
pòròò núú	corn, maize	Jamsay Douentza	Plains Dogon
dùmá jòò-gé	corn, maize	Tiranige	West Dogon

Nangan Dogon languages’ forms, Ben Tey *bàrměǰ* and Bankan Tey *bàràèmběj*, are composed of these languages’ lexemes for SORGHUM plus the word for ‘bush, outback’. While MAIZE in Fulfulde, *mbam(m)baari*, resembles these forms, I instead interpret it to be a genitive compound composed of the word for PIG *mba(a)m* (to be analyzed in forthcoming publications) in the related North Atlantic coastal language Wolof. Similarly, the word for MAIZE in Bangime, at first seeming closest to forms from Ben Tey and Bankan Tey, is analyzed here as a genitive compound (the *-n-* is the genitive marker in Bangime): *birò-n-dɔ́*. This term can be compared to another plant species *birò-n-só* which is composed of the form *birò*, meaning ‘shrub (*Guiera*)’, though the latter portions of these two compounds (*dɔ́* and *só*) are unknown.

Interestingly, the Dogon languages in which the word for MILLET is found in compounds for MAIZE are not those that use the *jó-* root for MILLET. That

TABLE 17 Dogon lexemes for 'wild sorghum' and 'corn'

Corn	Common wild sorghum	Language	Group
sàřà èmé	èmè sàřà	Yorno So	Escarpelement Dogon
sàřà èmbé	–	Tebul Ure	North Plateau Dogon
sàna èmè	èmà sàlálá	Yanda Dom	North Plateau Dogon
sàna èmmé	èmmè sàlálá	Tommo So	Escarpelement Dogon
sàm èmmé	èmmè sàdàlá	Donno So	Escarpelement Dogon
bàr mē-ǰ	èmè-ǰ sáará	Ben Tey	Nangan Dogon
bàrà èmbē-ǰ	èmbē-ǰ sáará	Bankan Tey	Nangan Dogon
bàrà èèmbé	èřè èèmbé	Perge Tegu	Plains Dogon
džàřà mbé	èmbè kójô	Nanga	Nangan Dogon
màn džàrà ñumà	pí kààna	Tomo Kan	Plains Dogon
màd èmbá-ŋgó	èmbà sàlálàà	Najamba	North Plateau Dogon
gìrì mbá-jè	èmbá sààrò	Ampari	West Dogon
èmbè dúlúmá	èmbà sáálà	Mombo	West Dogon
dílímà	sìindzá džàbà	Bunoge	West Dogon
dàlmà jò-gó		Penange	West Dogon
pòròd ñúú	èmè sáářá	Jamsay Douentza	Plains Dogon
sàmì jò-gò	èmmè sáálà	Dogul Dom	North Plateau Dogon

is, in the West Dogon language Tiranige Diga, the word for MILLET was shown to be from the root *see-* but MAIZE employs the word for MILLET that is found in North Escarpment languages such as Bondu So *jo-*. On the other hand, most Dogon groups who today live on the eastern side of the Escarpment use a word for MAIZE that actually derives from their languages' words for SORGHUM. These lexical patterns suggest that MAIZE was introduced to West Dogon factions not from eastern Dogon speakers, but directly by Western Mande speakers with whom they were later in contact.

Additional lexemes for 'corn' are compared with those for 'common wild sorghum' (*Sorghum arundinaceum*) among Dogon languages in 3.1 as the two forms are the same, with only the order of the two compounds differentiating the meaning.

Thus, the Bandiagara Cliffs languages – Dogon and Bangime – all attest lexemes for MAIZE comprising compounds which derive from other plants found

TABLE 18 Mande compounds for ‘corn’ and related varieties

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
mákkà	maïs	Soninke	Soninke-Bozo
m̩a̩a̩ n̩o̩	maïs	Korondougou	Soninke-Bozo
m̩a̩a̩ n̩o̩	maïs	Tieyaxo	Soninke-Bozo
m̩a̩a̩ n̩o̩	maïs	Tiema Cewe	Soninke-Bozo
saa n̩o̩	Guinea-Corn (bearing like Maize)	Yalunka	Susu-Yalunka
gbee n̩oo	Guinea-Corn (bearing like Maize)	Loko	Mende-Loko
wó̩jé̩ n̩ò̩ò̩	guinea corn	Vai	Manding-Vai

in the area. Those among the Dogon languages also refer to wild sorghum while Bangime has morphological parallels with at least one other plant species.

Among Mande Bozo varieties, compounds involving MILLET are also attested in terms for MAIZE. For example, the Korondougou lexeme is *m̩a̩a̩n̩o̩*. In fact, Mende and Guinea coast Mande languages share the same word as was illustrated to be so prevalent for MILLET, *n̩o̩* for MAIZE. Examples are provided in Table 18.

Here, the first part of these compounds could be a reduced form of the word for MAIZE in Soninke, *mákkà*, though Willett (1962: 7), who discusses early confusion over maize and sorghum, thought that the translation of the compound was, ‘large sorghum, sorghum of the master or chief’. Another hypothesis for the origin of the *maa* portion of the compound is discussed in relation to GROUND-NUT below. In any case, this first part of the word for MAIZE is shared with some Dogon languages such as Togo Kan *m̩a̩n̩è̩r̩è̩m̩á*, in which the second noun as SORGHUM again appears.

A different compound-initial noun is shared between the Mande language Jenaama *dàrà̩m̩à̩j̩v̩* and neighboring West Dogon languages Penange as *dàl-mà̩j̩ò̩g̩ó* and Bunoge *d̩l̩m̩à*, as well as the Nangan Dogon language’s form Nanga *d̩z̩à̩r̩à̩m̩bé*. This compound’s specific interpretation is also unknown but the suffix *-j̩v̩* and its allomorph *-lé̩v̩* appear with many flora species.

4.2.2 Extra-linguistic

It is clear that maize was domesticated about 9000 years ago in southwest Mexico (Matsuoka et al., 2002; Piperno et al., 2009). Therefore, the most likely location of its introduction into West Africa would be the Atlantic Coast from foreign traders in 16th century. Yet, Jeffreys (1971) argues, based on anthropological and ethnographic evidence, that corn goes back at least to the 12th century

explicitly among Mande groups. A date of introduction of MAIZE into BR was not located.

4.2.3 Summary

In the case of MAIZE, lexemes for plants already domesticated in West Africa have contributed to the creation of compounds. In line with the historical scenario, this necessitates that MAIZE was introduced to speakers of BR after indigenous crops were established. Additionally, although a form from Portuguese settlers (see RICE below) or other non-native terms would be expected based on historical scenarios for the introduction of maize into West Africa, in fact, we find compounds which incorporate native terms.

It may be that, because maize is not a frequently cultivated crop among the Dogon or the Bangande, its lexeme was created from other plants' species names after the first farming practices were already established. In other words, the data thus far shown for ancient grains such as pearl millet, fonio, and sorghum show close contact between Dogon, Bangime, and Mande speakers was taking place possibly prior to settlement of the Bandiagara Escarpment. In contrast, if the settlement timeline of BR is correct, maize could not have been introduced to BR populations except after they had already begun to inhabit the Escarpment (purportedly around 800 years ago). The following subsection introduces the first non-grain crop of the current study.

4.5 *OKRA 'okra' Abelmoschus esculentus*

As noted in the previous subsection, some languages in the study use forms for OKRA in compounds for CORN. Furthermore, the patterning for OKRA closely resembles that of SORGHUM suggesting similar time depths and contact events for these two crops among BR languages.

4.5.1 Linguistic

In contrast to the geographic patterning seen thus far for Dogon lexemes for MAIZE and MILLET, and slightly different than SORGHUM, OKRA shows a split across the Escarpment along north-south lines rather than east-west. Comparative examples are shown in Map 10.

As noted above, the patterning for OKRA is similar to that of SORGHUM; Bangime clearly shares a form with surrounding Dogon languages, which in turn share a word from Mande languages within the Manding subgroup. The form codified in the accompanying map as GAD has reflexes which begin with [m] as in Bangime *mààdʒí* or as either *mánààdʒi* or *gáŋgádʒi* in Tommo So. Additionally, as shown in the extended map, this lexical root is pervasive throughout West African languages.

MAP 10 OKRA in BR

TABLE 19 OKRA comparative lexemes in Bangime, South Dogon, Gur, Atlantic, and Manding

Gloss	Form	Language	Group
okra	mààdʒí	Bangime	Isolate
okra	mààndʒí	Tiranige	West Dogon
okra	gáŋgádʒí	Yorno So	Escarpment Dogon
okra	gáŋáázi	Dogul Dom	North-Plateau Dogon
okra	gagaare (sg)		
(pod of <i>Hibiscus esculentus</i>)	gaŋadʒi (pl)	Fulfulde	North Atlantic
gombo	dʒàxà táŋŋè	Soninke	Soninke-Bozo
gombo	xándʒá	Khassonké	West-Manding
gombo	gbámá	Sourani	Gur
gombo okra	gbánsà	Lélé	Central Mande
okra gombo	gbáŋ	Koro	Central Mande
gombo	gbá	Dioula	East-Manding
Hibiscus esculentus, gombo	gá	Bambara	East-Manding
okra	wāā	Jenaama	Soninke-Bozo

Abelmoschus esculentus ‘okra’ wāā, and *Hibiscus sabdariffa* ‘roselle variety’ wó-bēŋ in Jenaama are slightly reminiscent of the form for FONIO in Bangime. By analogy, *Panicum laetum* ‘wild fonio’ has the same name as cultivated okra in West Dogon languages including Bunoge and Tiranige pógó.

Among the Dogon languages, a transition from [g] to [m] would be difficult to explain if not for these East-Manding stems with [gb] initial sequences. That is, I propose that the word in the West Dogon languages is derived from a form such as *gbáw̃* in the East Manding language Koro. Labial-velar segments are not found in Dogon languages (or Bangime), so a reinterpretation of the initial consonant as either a bilabial or a velar makes sense.

Further, the final nasalized vowel or glide in the East Manding languages and Jenaama Bozo hints to the loss of a nasal at some point in the evolution of this word. Proto-Central-Gur reconstructs 'okra' as **man*,²¹ and Pozdniakov (2022) posits the Proto-Fula-Sereer form for 'okra' as *gandz* or *gana*. It appears as if each of these languages borrowed an early form of this lexeme and then innovations in the stem-initial consonant followed.

The *-dzi* ending that is associated with these lexemes is likely a component of a compound or a noun class suffix from the donor language (compare forms for GROUNDNUT *tigadzɛ*, MILLET *kénigé* SORGHUM and *èrè-gè* RICE). Note that in the North-Plateau Dogon language Bondu So, while *góŋ-gó* is the lexeme for OKRA, *mánáà* in the language refers to a 'cooked meal'. Thus, for example, the Tiranige Diga form *mànàdzí* may be composed of an older Dogon root for MEAL, plus a residual noun class marker. This semantic shift has already been witnessed between Bangime and the Bozo languages words for FONIO and MEAL.

As noted above, some Dogon languages of the northeastern quadrant of the Escarpment resisted this persistent lexical root. Not only that, but the root found among these Dogon languages, coded on the codified version of Map 10 and exemplified in Table 20, is actually not only limited to those languages or that area.

This second lexeme for OKRA appears across eastern Mali, but also in some languages currently spoken in Guinea. By examining the expanded version of Map 10, a third form attests a scattered distribution among unrelated languages and disparate locations.

Yet, similar to the case of FONIO wherein seemingly separate forms actually have a shared source at a deeper level, as with lexemes beginning with [m] and [g] being from the same source **GAD**, the codified forms **BOD** and **GOB** actually likely represent a common source. Phototactically, it is of importance to note that the stem-initial velar [g, k, x], bilabial [m], and labio-velar [w] consonants can only be attributed back to a common source in the labial-velar plosive [gb]. Vai, for instance, is a language which retains this realization.

21 Though Gur languages were not fully integrated into the core group for this study, they will be in future investigations.

TABLE 20 OKRA comparative lexemes across language families

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
póró	okra	Ben Tey	Nangan Dogon
póró	okra	Jamsay	Plains Dogon
póló-j	okra	Bankan Tey	Nangan Dogon
bòndò	okra	Kono	Kpelle
bòndó	okra, hibiscus esculentus	Mende	Mende-Loko
ḡḡdò	gombo gombo	Zialo	Western Mande
ḡḡḡ	gombo	Mayaa	Samo (Mande)
ḡḡḡḡḡḡ	okra	Vai	Manding-Vai
ḡḡḡḡḡ	okra	Mumuye (Zing)	Mumuyic
ḡḡḡ	gombo	Pana	Gur

4.5.1 Extra-linguistic

The first site of okra domestication is still debated. A West African origin of okra was established by Hamon and Van Stolen (1989) based on genetic data, but more recent studies suggest Ethiopia as the first site of domestication (Mohammed et al., 2020). The closest evidence of okra cultivation to BR was found by Bigga and Kahlheber (2011) at Mege (Lake Chad) 2600 years ago.

4.5.2 Summary

There appears to be much more variation in the regional lexemes for OKRA than, for example, those found in Central Africa among the Bantu languages spoken there, suggesting a greater time depth in BR. As with ‘fonio’, the lexeme from which the term ‘gumbo’ in English and ‘gombo’ in French surely derives, *ḡḡḡḡḡ*, is found across Bantu and other languages of Cameroon such as Mumuye.

4.6 RICE ‘African rice’ *Oryza glaberrima*

The lexical patterns of RICE are the most prolific throughout BR than any crop thus far discussed, with the exception of unique terms in Bozo Jenaama and Bangime.

MAP 11 RICE in BR

TABLE 21 Dogon comparative lexemes for RICE

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
édé	rice	Ampari	West Dogon
èrè-gè	rice	Tiranige Diga	West Dogon
árá	rice	Bankan Tey	Nangan Dogon
ʔàrá	rice	Tomo Kan	West Dogon
áárá	rice	Ben Tey	Nangan Dogon
ádá	Rice	Yanda Dom	North-Plateau Dogon

4.6.1 Linguistic

Forms for RICE, ‘African rice’ *Oryza glaberrima*, are known to be widespread homogenous words across West Africa. The form from Macina Fulfulde shown in the excerpt from the Map 11 above, *maaro*, is found throughout unrelated West African languages.

However, as in the case of MILLET, Bangime has resisted this overwhelmingly common loan word, as has neighboring Bozo language Jenaama where the form *dūgā* is attested. Other than the form for OKRA mentioned above, the only term with any resemblance to Bangime *gómè* in the database is *góbé* from Mende, ‘a variety of rice’.

As displayed on Map 11 and the examples in Table 21, the Dogon languages are again split geographically between the east and west sides of the Escarpment as in the case of most of the other lexemes for crops presented in this article save for OKRA. If the forms found among the Dogon languages are of the same source as *maaro*, the initial consonant would have been lost. This would

TABLE 23 Comparative lexemes for RICE

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
maano	rice plant	Gubaher	North Atlantic
maano	le riz. (avant d'être pilé) entier	Bainouk	North Atlantic
mààlō	riz	Balante	Atlantic-Bak
maalō	rice	Gambian Wolof	North Atlantic
mālōŋ	riz	Bedik	North Atlantic
mālōŋ	rice	Jogo	Manding-Jogo
maano	riz non pilé	Guñaamolo	North Atlantic
ε-maano	riz	Joola bliss	Atlantic-Bak
maaro	riz (générique) cultivé	Peul (Macina)	North Atlantic
màlō	rice (as crop) / riz (culture)	Koro	East-Manding
malo	le riz	Non	North Atlantic
maalo	rice	Sereer (Saalum)	North Atlantic
máálō	rice (uncooked)	Wolof	North Atlantic
máló	riz	Koyaga	East-Manding
mááro	rice (Cooked)	Mandinka	West-Manding
máarò	riz	Soninke	Soninke-Bozo
máálù	riz	Maninka du Niokolo	West-Manding

ma-, lexemes which may be codified as DO with the meaning ‘food’ are unattested in the current database. As the author states that the “Kwa” were the first inhabitants of the Niger Delta, he may be referring to those today classified as speaking an Ijoid language. Rather, in the Ijoid language Nembe, for example, we find the form *ɔ̀r̀s̀ì* for ‘rice’ (also see the Dogon language Najamba in Table 22 above) and *fìàì* ‘solid food; meal; eatables’.

There is one additional lexeme for RICE in West Africa discussed in this study. Both Portères (1959a) and Blench (2006) provide examples, including variants such as those provided here from the database in Table 24, yet ascribe them to a common source with those shown in Table 23.

The lexemes codified as BAD in orange and BO in green on the expanded map found in the supplemental materials form a split, with distributions along the West Atlantic coastal regions and the Niger River respectively. As shown through examples drawn from the database used in this study in Tables 25–26, both sets span myriad language families.

Given the geographic and genealogical spread of these lexemes, the forms are clearly loan words. Most researchers who have discussed this feature – a

TABLE 24 Comparative lexemes for RICE

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
móò	riz	Dendi	Eastern Songhay
mòò	rice	Senni	Eastern Songhay
móó	rice	Tondi Kiini	Eastern Songhay
mòó	riz	Kaado (Ayorou-Goungokore)	Eastern Songhay
mòó	riz	Zarma	Eastern Songhay
mòò	riz	Sembla	Western Mande

nearly areal attestation of one lexical stem across West and Western Africa – attribute the source of the loan among unrelated languages to Mande (Blench, 2006; Watson, 2018 with specific reference to Atlantic languages), or even Proto-Mande (Childs, 2002). As with the proposed significant time depth for forms for FONIO, Blench (2006: 219) states,

There is one West African root that seems to be very widespread and to be embedded in Niger-Congo languages and to be borrowed into Nilo-Saharan which is indicative of this older layer of rice cultivation.

Now turning to extra-linguistic sources for the timeline for the domestication of rice in West Africa, we do find that African rice is quite ancient.

4.6.2 Extra-linguistic

African rice (*Oryza glaberrima*) was first domesticated around 3000 years ago (Wang et al., 2014). The exact location of the inception of domesticated African rice is still disputed today (Wambugu, Ndjiondjop, and Henry, 2021). Two scenarios have been proposed. The first is particularly pertinent to this study; a theory first put forth by Portères (1962) continues to find support. He suggests that African rice was first cultivated in an area near BR, specifically at Djenné-Djeno in the Middle Niger Delta – this is also supported by archeological evidence (McIntosh and McIntosh, 1981) – from whence it subsequently spread to the Atlantic coast. The second theory proposes geographically disparate origins of domestication (Harlan, De Wet, and Stemler, 1976).

Recent genetic analyses (Wang et al., 2014; Veltman et al., 2019) support Portères' (1962) early hypothesis of ancient rice cultivation in the Inland Delta of the upper Niger river, with subsequent diversification to Atlantic coastal regions, yet Veltman et al. (2019) also caution that there were likely additional,

therefore multiple, centers of domestication. The latter authors offer a third scenario consisting of two primary domestication events: one in the Inner Niger Delta and one in the modern-day Guinea Highlands.

As noted above, Proto-Mande is estimated to have been spoken at least 5000 years ago in what is now the country of Mauritania (Vydrin, 2009). At a date of 3000 years ago, Proto-Soninke-Bozo speakers indeed may have been farming rice in the Inland Niger Delta. Gallais (1984) states that the Marka, which he defines as being a pre-ethnic society formed from early Soninke groups of the Ghana Empire (see comments regarding the speakers of Jenaama in section 2), were the first to farm rice in the basins of the Niger River Delta. The Mande Bozo varieties attest *dūgā* (Bandiagara cliffs) and *dúgó* (Djenne) which appear not to be shared with other languages in the database.

The first Portuguese to reach Africa remarked on rice cultivation among Atlantic-speaking communities of the Upper Guinea Coast in the second half of the 15th century (Linares, 2002). This author (2002) further notes that,

Although it is not known with certainty when and where the first varieties of Asian rice *O. sativa* were first introduced into West Africa, the general consensus is that, beginning in the 16th century, the species spread and was adopted by peoples living in the Upper Guinea Coast who had previous experience growing the local African species.

LINARES, 2002: 361.

That is, a replacement of local rice took place following the introduction of non-native species sometime from the later 15th to 16th centuries, and thus a loan word is expected.

4.6.3 Summary

It is tentatively proposed here that early terms for RICE may have been replaced with the Portuguese lexeme along with the replacement of the rice species itself. The majority of languages that attest the widespread form *maaro*, including Soninke *máaro*, are spoken on the Atlantic coast. Note that, in Soninke, there are no indigenous terms that start with the vowel [a]. Thus, if indeed from Portuguese *arroz*, an integrated loanword into Soninke would require the addition of a consonant onset. The addition of the initial nasal [m] still requires explanation, but Soninke could also be a plausible propagator of the loan to other speakers of West Africa.

Rice farmers who speak Mande or Atlantic languages have rich vocabularies for different rice varieties. This widespread lexeme merely masks the richness of the native terminology. Nevertheless, given the similarity in form across lan-

MAP 12 Lexemes for YAM in BR

guages and the time depth of the associated grain RICE, it is likely that, as with the case of MILLET, Mande-speaking traders or merchants relatively recently proliferated the lexeme for RICE with a foreign grain which has supplanted the original diversity of the crop and its terminology. Future studies will look further into taxonomies of these crops' cultivars.

4.7 *YAM, CASSAVA, and SWEET POTATO* 'yam' *Dioscorea rotundata*, 'cassava' *Manihot esculenta*, and 'sweet potato' *Ipomoea batatas*

As with maize and yam, *Dioscorea rotundata* and similar rhizomes are not native to BR and thus are likely sources for loan words. In particular, sweet potato, *Ipomoea batatas*, is an imported crop. However, as in the case of words for MAIZE, we see in this subsection that lexemes for CASSAVA and SWEET POTATO are compounds composed of the word for YAM. Yet, in contrast to MAIZE, the word for YAM is highly homogenous throughout most of the study area.

4.7.1 Linguistic

As shown on Map 12, terms for YAM, CASSAVA, and SWEET POTATO throughout most of West Africa are composed of one dominant form, here codified as KU.

With regards to this root for YAM, Blench (2006: 130) states, "West African Niger-Congo terms suggest some antiquity for a root of the shape #-ku", but further notes, "The root appears to be absent in Gur and Atlantic languages but otherwise spreads from Mande to Bantu, indicating its salience over a wide swathe of the continent" (131).

Examples drawn from the database used in this study in Table 25 do illustrate this root appearing in some Gur languages (though, as noted above, this study has yet to fully incorporate the group into the core BR sample); there are

TABLE 25 Comparative lexemes for YAM

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
kùù	yam	Bangime	Isolate
kúù	yam	Perge Tegu	Plains Dogon
kùú	yam	Yorno So	Escarpment Dogon
kúú	yam	Dogul Dom	North-Plateau Dogon
kúù	yam	Tondi Kiini	Eastern Songhay
kúù	cultivated yam	Humburi Senni	Eastern Songhay
kūù	yam	Jenaama	Soninke-Bozo
ku	yam	Fulfulde	North Atlantic
kú	igname	Pana	Gur

admittedly few instances among Atlantic languages. It is noteworthy that ‘yam sp. *Dioscorea*’ is also reconstructed in Proto-Bantu as *kòá but that Kastenholz (1996) gives the form **gao/jao* for Proto-Mande.

Yams are cultivated less frequently in BR than areas further south. Thus, the word for YAM as *KU* in Bangime and the Dogon languages is certainly a loan, likely again proliferated by Mande farmers and traders. The lack of phonetic variation suggests the introduction of YAM was more recent than, for example, MAIZE. The preference for the long vowel among the Dogon languages and Bangime is due to bimoraicity requirements in monosyllabic words, though the low tones on the Bangime root may indicate the borrowing is directly from Jenaama rather than Dogon as the latter languages do not have any low-toned mono-morphemic lexemes.

Words for CASSAVA *Manihot esculenta* and SWEET POTATO *Ipomoea batatas* are compounds with a wide distribution using the same root as that shown for YAM with examples given in Table 26.

It is curious to note that there is a split between words for CASSAVA and SWEET POTATO. The former meaning attests compounds with *bana* and the latter with *masa* among most of the languages in the sample, yet in some of the Dogon languages, the forms can refer to either tuber. The proposed reason for this is a reinterpretation of the word *bán* which means ‘red’ among these same Dogon languages and thus accurately depicts a ‘red yam’ as a sweet potato.

The effect of the form *KU* specifically on BR and surrounding languages can be seen when comparing forms for SWEET POTATO and CASSAVA in the Songhay of Hombori and Djenne with other Songhay languages in which the forms have been influenced from Hausa (cf. comments by Blench, 2006: 135). Table 27

TABLE 26 Comparative lexemes for YAM, CASSAVA, and SWEET POTATO

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
bà̀nà̀ṅ kù̀ù	cassava, manioc	Bangime	Isolate
bà̀nà̀ṅ kṳ̀ṳ̀	manioc	Jenaama	Soninke-Bozo
bà̀nà̀ṅ kú	cassava, manioc	Bunoge	West Dogon
bá̀nà̀ṅ kù	cassava, manioc	Tondi Kiini	Eastern Songhay
banan ku	manioc	Macina Fulfulde	North Atlantic
banda kuu	manioc	San	East-Manding
banḡ kṳṳḡ	manioc	Sénoufo	Gur
bà̀nà̀ kúú	sweet potato	Yorno So	Escarpment Dogon
bana hu	manioc	Tieyaxo Bozo	Soninke-Bozo
màsà kú̀ù	sweet potato	Jamsay	Plains Dogon
màsà kṳ̀ù	sweet potato	Jenaama	Soninke-Bozo
màsá kú̀ù	sweet potato	Tiranige Diga	West Dogon
màsá kú̀ù	cultivated sweet potato	Tondi Kiini	Eastern Songhay
màsà kú	patate douce	Kong Dioula	East-Manding
màsà kṳ̀	patate douce	Bobo	Western Mande
masa ku	patate	Sénoufo	Gur

illustrates two lexemes that emerged due to contact between Songhay speakers and those of languages spoken in Cameroon and Nigeria respectively.

These forms for YAM and CASSAVA from other Eastern Songhay languages illustrate that the forms found in the Songhay languages spoken in BR have been influenced therein by Mande (and/or Dogon) languages. This specific clustering suggests that YAM and CASSAVA were introduced into BR following the split between these Songhay varieties.

4.7.3 Extra-linguistic

Kahlheber et al. (2009) as well as Blench (2009) note the importance of different yam species to West African farmers and that, among the many crops grown there today, yams are indigenous to (Central) West Africa, that is, further south than the Bandiagara Escarpment where the languages in our core sample are spoken today. Blench (2009: 23) specifically discusses that which he refers to as ‘aerial yam’ *Dioscorea bulbifera*, stating linguistic evidence points to its domestication around 3000–4000 years BP, though he does not indicate a locality (Blench, 2009).

TABLE 27 Eastern Songhay comparative lexemes for YAM and CASSAVA

Form	Gloss	Language
dùndù	igname	Kaado
dùndú	igname	Dendi
dùndù	igname	Zarma
òróggò	manioc, manihot utilissima (euphorbiacées)	Kaado
ɾóóggò	manioc	Dendi
róóggò	manioc	Zarma

The species of yam that is native to Central West Africa is *Dioscorea rotundata*, though, as noted by Blench (2006: 130), linguistic sources often list other subspecies such as *Dioscorea*. Brooks (1986) comments that yams were probably domesticated during the time of rice domestication, thus around 3000 years ago. Scarcelli et al.'s (2019) phylogenetic study of yam genomics supports their being first originating in the Niger River basin.

Sweet potatoes, on the other hand, as mentioned in the introduction to this section, were likely brought by foreign traders – probably the Portuguese (Low et al., 2009) – relatively recently (around 500 years ago).

4.7.3 Summary

The linguistic evidence shown here points to a link between Mande traders and cultivators of yams of the more southern regions where Proto-Bantu was once spoken, but with a recent introduction into the Bangime- and Dogon-speaking area, probably by Mande traders. That is, in contrast to RICE, where Bangime and Jenaama attest words which have resisted Mande and/or Dogon influence, these forms are uniformly widespread across the Bandiagara Escarpment. Older terms demonstrated throughout this article such as those for MILLET are much more diverse, and FONIO has many more reflexes. Words for SWEET POTATO and CASSAVA are also clearly recent Mande loans which have also proliferated the Dogon languages and Bangime. In comparison with plants that have undergone a similar trajectory to West Africa such as MAIZE and RICE above and GROUNDNUT below, words for SWEET POTATO among the sample of West African languages are almost categorically compounds based on the word for YAM with little divergence from the probable Mande language source. These diverging patterns suggest that, while imported foods into the West Africa Atlantic coast from Portuguese merchants may have arrived at the same time

TABLE 28 Comparative lexemes for GROUNDNUT coded as TIG

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
tìgá	<i>Arachis hypogaea</i> , arachide	Bambara	East-Manding
tìgâ	arachide	Soninke	Soninke-Bozo
tìga	arachide	Pular	North Atlantic
tíká	arachide	Bedik	North Atlantic
má-tígá	arachide	Bambara	East-Manding
maa-tige	arachide	Bozo (Korondougou nord)	Soninke-Bozo
ká-tígá	<i>Arachis hypogaea</i> , arachide	Bambara	East-Manding
tìgà ndéppè	pois de terre	Soninke	Soninke-Bozo
tìgàdzí dàbbè	ground nut	Bangime	Isolate

The second form codified broadly as GED on the coded version of Map 13 is found among languages at the western-most edge of the Atlantic family's region, but, surprisingly, also among the Dogon languages. Comparative examples across language families are given in Table 29.

Despite a great geographic distance between Atlantic-Bak languages and Dogon communities, forms such as Huluf *egélete* and Dogul Dom *égilè* are nearly identical.²² Williamson (1970: 161) cites a form *ahó ékééré* found in the “extreme Eastern Delta” which she states is a loan word from Southern Igbo. This is a promising eventual source for the lexemes codified as GED. In Brosnahan's (1967) wordlist of the Delta Cross language Gokana, a form *àhānkéré* is also listed, but therein is attributed to a borrowing event. As will be further discussed in a subsequent publication, in Bangime, the likely linked *kērē-bè* is a ‘wild cow-pea’ *Vigna sp.* Among languages which attest these forms, we do not find many from the Mande group, suggesting that there was a separate distribution event than that of the Mande Expansion which likely proliferated the lexeme shown above in Table 28.

An additional form for GROUNDNUT is found among Songhay languages. Similar to the case stated above for Bangime, regarding examples provided in

22 Most Atlantic languages do not have tones, and a *t ~ l* alternation is present among many Jóola languages intervocalically.

TABLE 29 Comparative lexemes for GROUNDNUT coded as TIG

Form	Gloss	Language	Group
gerte	Arachide	Wolof	North Atlantic
hu-gerete	arachide	Her	North Atlantic
ε-gelete	arachide	Huluf	Jóola (Atlantic-Bak)
ε-gerette	arachide	Bandial	Jóola (Atlantic-Bak)
ε-kereta	arachide	Gusiilaay	Jóola (Atlantic-Bak)
éǵilè	peanut or groundnut	Dogul Dom	North-Plateau Dogon
élè	peanut or groundnut	Donno So	Escarpment Dogon
ééré	peanut or groundnut	Gourou	Plains Dogon
ééré	peanut or groundnut	Jamsay	Plains Dogon
ééré	peanut or groundnut	Togo-Kan	Plains Dogon
élé-ŋgó	peanut or groundnut	Najamba	North-Plateau Dogon
élé kèlè	peanut or groundnut	Tommo So	Escarpment Dogon

Table 30, Souag (2012: 206) comments that the word in Songhay (at least Tondi Kiini) is also borrowed into Berber, but with the meaning ‘pea’. According to Koelle’s (1854) wordlist, the other form in Humburi Senni is apparently another borrowed lexeme from Mossi which attests *sunkaama*.

Furthermore, as with RICE, the separate forms for GROUNDNUT found among West African languages can be attributed to separate species of the legume. These separate species of cultivated peanuts and groundnuts are discussed briefly below. Again, it is important to note that even though widespread lexemes have infiltrated most West African groups, Songhay languages remain apart from the effects of the Mande Expansion in this regard.

4.8.3 Extra-linguistic

Similar to the situation for RICE, terms for ‘Bambara groundnut’ are now conflated with those for ‘peanut’ *Arachis hypogaea*; like MAIZE and SWEET POTATO, the latter was recently imported from the Americas by the Portuguese.

As its name suggests, the source of ‘Bambara groundnut’ *Vigna subterranea* was originally attributed to Mali, but its most diverse genetic structure has recently been confirmed in the area of northern Cameroon or north-eastern Nigeria, and hence probably originates there (Majola, Gerrano, and Shimelis, 2021). Temegne Nono et al. (2018) add that no wild forms of groundnuts have been found in Mali. The time depth of the groundnut in BR was not found,

TABLE 30 Comparative lexemes for GROUNDNUT in Songhay languages

Form	Gloss	Language
sùṅkáám-ò	cultivated peanut	Humburi Senni
dáms-ó	groundnut	Humburi Senni
dáms-í	peanuts	Tondi Kiini
tóndì dámís-í	groundnut	Humburi Senni

though Blench (2009: 25) cites archaeobotanical evidence for its presence in Burkina Faso to ca. 1800 BP.

4.8.4 Summary

It is likely that terms for RICE also attest secondary forms, but in the case of GROUNDNUT, two lexemes have become common place, with a split between the major language groups, Mande and Atlantic. This suggests, as was indicated within the discussion of SWEET POTATO above, that not only did Mande, but also Atlantic-language speaking traders, diffuse crops along with their names to other West African populations. The clear connection between the Dogon languages' word for GROUNDNUT and that of Atlantic language speakers with whom they are in no apparent contact today is of particular interest and will be explored through further investigations.

5 Discussion

This study traces a similar path to that of Bostoen (2007b) who considers many of the same plant terms among Zambian languages, and mimics the methods of Robbeets et al. (2021) who follow the dispersal of lexemes for millet and other cereals across Asia. While Bostoen's comparison and reconstruction techniques cannot be implemented in the case of such genealogically isolated languages as those which form the core group used in this study, the current investigation goes beyond Robbeets' triangulation of archaeology, genetics, and linguistics to include additional invaluable insights from anthropologists, ethnographers, and historians. That is, through consultation with external archaeological, historical, and genetic resources, each plant species name is associated with an estimated date of introduction into West Africa, or specifically to BR where available. These extra-linguistic sources were consulted to

attempt to determine which language was likely spoken at the estimated time period and in the area where a plant – or, in future publications, an animal’s – domestication first took place.

In line with the theory of center of origin of plant species (Harlan, 1971), this study has found that the most ancient African domesticated grains – pearl millet, sorghum, possibly fonio, as well as okra – attest the most diverse lexemes. At the same time, the effects of far-reaching trade networks are witnessed in the widespread dispersal of Mande-language lexemes. The Mande Expansion, much less known than its Bantu analogue, is attributed with the proliferation of terms for MILLET, SORGHUM, and FONIO across unrelated languages of West Africa.

An exception to the generalization that native cultivated plants illustrate diverse nomenclature is found among words for RICE, which consistently seems to apply a borrowed term. As in the case of PEANUT (GROUNDNUT), however, I postulate that non-native rice and groundnut species have supplanted indigenous ones along with their names. Yet, surprisingly, words for other imported plants such as MAIZE and SWEET POTATO are formed of compounds employing already existing domesticated plant species rather than adopting foreign names for these extraneous foods, suggesting that, at least in the case of MAIZE, the source of this domesticate may be closer to area than is currently thought.

The Bandiagara Region is an critical area of West Africa for which we are fortunate to have a relative wealth of information from various disciplines. Yet, we still do not know from whence came the inhabitants of this richly diverse region. The Dogon languages alone number in the twenties at least. The Bandiagara Escarpment itself represents a rocky terrain, and a natural east-west divide separates groups living along either side of the cliff. This division leads to close contact among easily accessible villages, but less frequent interactions with those who live in places that are hard to reach. This situation – in part – causes speakers’ languages to, on the one hand, converge, while at the same time, pushing other languages to diverge.

Among early crop terms, we find spheres of influence change depending on a variety of factors, including the time depth and presumed location of a plant’s introduction. Words for FONIO, for example, are largely uniform throughout the Dogon languages of the Escarpment, suggesting the term proliferated a proto form of the language that was spoken before the speakers’ settlement of the area. On the contrary, it is only the eastern side of the Cliff that terms for MILLET resembling those of East-Manding (Mande) languages spoken generally to the south of BR are found, with a small pocket of West Dogon languages attesting a separate term that appears to have no external source. According to

extra-linguistic evidence, the use of pearl millet dominated the area before that of fonio. Indeed, it is probable that the cliffs were settled in waves rather than all at once as these patterns suggest. The opposite distribution holds true for SORGHUM, wherein the somewhat secluded western enclaves use a term that is almost identical to the word found in more southerly East-Manding (Mande) languages, whereas speakers along the eastern edges of the Escarpment use a term that may have an eventual, distant, source in either Nilotic or Bantu languages. In this case, the potential is there for a direct correspondence with extra-linguistic evidence as it is probable that sorghum was first domesticated far to the east in modern-day Sudan.

In each crop's case, we also find that the language isolate Bangime and its closest Mande-speaking neighbors of the Soninke-Bozo subgroup have likely been in contact since antiquity. Directly shared lexemes such as that for MILLET between Bangime and Bozo languages to the exclusion of those from Dogon varieties suggests that their speakers' contact preceded at least the Dogon peoples' settlement of the Bandiagara Escarpment where both the Bangande and Dogon make their homes today.

Furthermore, various Dogon groups are shown to have had contact with both Mande populations and the Bangande at separate stages in history, further substantiating the claim that the Bangande and Dogon settled their current homes along and atop the Bandiagara Escarpment in stages rather than as a single event.

6 Conclusion

This study has found that there are several types of loan word distributions in the West African agricultural context: those that have an areal distribution, and others that retain deep diversity. Some borrowing patterns for lexemes such as those for MILLET, FONIO, and OKRA are likely the result of early domestication in West Africa, with subsequent far-reaching trade networks. Others, like RICE and GROUNDNUT attest a split in terminology that is attributed to the relatively recent – foreign – introduction of non-native species that have, over time, come to replace indigenous crops and terminology among many language groups. Specifically, Jenaama Bozo and Bangime may preserve their own forms that thus far cannot be traced to an external source, though in some of these cases, such as OKRA and RICE, the source is not in another language, but in another concept where a shift in meaning has taken place. Furthermore, even among languages with seemingly non-borrowed vocabulary such as terms for FONIO, OKRA, and RICE, these are in fact likely due to semantic shifts rather than replacement.

Blench (2006: 70) argues that,

It can therefore be assumed that all the principal diversification and the establishment of the major branches of Niger-Congo occurred while speakers were still using hunting, fishing and gathering as the principal subsistence strategy.

Rather, through the evidence put forth in this article and from the larger study to which this paper is drawn, I believe that West African ethnicities are inextricably tied to occupation, and that occupational roles in turn rely on long-term agricultural practices.

Furthermore, contrary to early statements by Blench (2007) in reference to Bangime, all of the languages of BR, especially Bangime, abound in shared vocabulary with unrelated languages in the agricultural domain. This research has contributed to the conversation on West African early agriculture by revising outdated material concerning Bangime and the Dogon languages and their speakers' interactions with Mande populations. These data have been combined with up-to-date cross-disciplinary materials. This study was timed to take advantage of the peak of resources available across disciplines from the Bandiagara Escarpment.

In subsequent work, not only will additional evidence of language contact in the form of loan words for crop concepts be discussed, but also from domesticated animals as well as cultural concepts, such as iron, and other materials that are relied upon in the area.

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